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Impacts of integrated mobility concepts in residential complexes on residents' travel behavior

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ABSTRACT

Car-based mobility is a significant contributor to inefficient land use, global carbon emissions, and air pollution, exacerbating urban challenges such as congestion and mobility inequality. Integrated Mobility Concepts (IMCs) in residential complexes have emerged as a promising solution, combining urban planning with sustainable transport strategies through both restrictive (push) and incentive-based (pull) measures to reduce car dependency in residential complexes. This study investigates the impact of IMCs on travel behavior by analyzing survey data from 911 residents across 19 residential complexes in Switzerland, spanning both urban and suburban contexts. The methodology involved comparing mobility patterns between 10 complexes with IMCs and 9 without, utilizing both traditional statistical methods and machine learning models. Descriptive statistics and t-tests were used for group comparisons, while multivariate regression and machine learning techniques, such as Random Forest and Lasso regression, were applied to identify key predictors of car ownership and use. The results show that urban complexes with IMCs experience 39% lower car ownership and significantly reduced reliance on private motorized transport (9% of trips, compared to 17% in conventional complexes). Parking availability was identified as the most critical factor influencing car ownership and transport behavior, with a pronounced self-selection effect where residents with sustainable mobility preferences are more likely to choose these complexes. These findings emphasize the need for context-specific mobility solutions, as the impact of IMCs is heterogeneous and varies across different demographic and spatial contexts.

1. Introduction

The growing concerns about environmental degradation, urban sprawl, and climate change have placed extensive pressure on societies to rethink the role of mobility, particularly car-based mobility. The prevailing car-centric mobility paradigm, still predominantly fossil fuel-based, contributes substantially to a range of social and environmental issues, including mobility injustice, energy poverty, noise pollution, air pollution, land consumption, and carbon emissions. Urban and fast-growing suburban areas are especially vulnerable, where traffic congestion leads to increased emissions and deteriorating air quality. Our world's cities are responsible for

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70 % of global carbon emissions while consuming two-thirds of global energy, and are thus recognized as a key area for the reduction of energy consumption and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (Winkler et al., 2023). The transportation sector plays a crucial role in this. Globally, transportation is responsible for approximately one-quarter of total GHG emissions, with passenger road transport accounting for a significant portion (45 %) of that share (Ritchie & Roser, 2024). In this paper's regional context, namely Switzerland, transport accounts for 31 % (excluding air travel) of the country's GHG emissions (Federal Office for the Environment FOEN, 2023). Despite a world-famous railway and one of Europe's most advanced and reliable public transportation systems, Switzerland has a very high motorization rate of 54 % and a distance-based private motorized transport (PMT) mode share of 70 % (FSO, 2023b).

Fast population growth and urban sprawl in many countries, especially Switzerland, exacerbate these challenges by increasing the demand for land and encouraging car dependency. In many cities, cars dominate public space, leaving less room for green spaces and pedestrian zones and bicycling paths. According to Gössling (2020), a parked car uses three times more space than public transport and ten times more than a bicycle, while at 50 km/h (a common inner-city speed limit in many European countries), it requires 70 times more space than a cyclist or pedestrian, highlighting the impact of speed on space use. This land consumption not only degrades urban ecosystems but also impairs the quality of life of urban residents. Meanwhile, car ownership further entrenches societal norms that prioritize individual vehicle use, reinforcing unsustainable practices. These factors necessitate a shift from car-centric urban planning as well as a transition towards more sustainable forms of transportation in densely populated urban and growing suburban areas.

In response to these challenges, key stakeholders such as governments at state and municipal level, housing developers, and transport planners, among others, have begun exploring innovative mobility strategies to catalyze the sustainable mobility transition and to reduce car dependency.

Therefore, cities and municipalities usually employ a variety of measures such as promotion of active mobility (walking and cycling), improving public transportation, low emission zones or even zero emission zones (LEZ/ZEZ), congestion charging, promotion of shared mobility solutions, et cetera.

Among one of the most promising measures, having grown in popularity among municipal governments and housing developers since the 1990s, are car-reduced or even car-free residential complexes (Küchel et al., 2024). Contrary to conventional urban developments, car-reduced neighborhoods usually feature a so-called "Integrated Mobility Concept" (henceforth "IMC") (Schróder & Klinger, 2024). By definition, an IMC seeks to integrate urban development and transport planning while applying a combination of restrictive ("push") measures and incentive-based ("pull") measures to reduce car dependency (Heldt et al., 2021). Push measures are restrictive policies that aim to reduce car use by increasing costs, limiting availability, or implementing regulatory constraints, such as reduced parking spaces, higher parking fees, congestion pricing, or urban access restrictions (Hekler et al., 2022). These measures discourage car use by making it less convenient or more expensive. Pull measures are incentive-based strategies designed to encourage sustainable mobility by making alternatives more attractive, such as improved public transport, expanded cycling infrastructure, shared mobility services, or subsidies for public transit passes (Hekler et al., 2022; Meyer, 1999).

These strategies are particularly evident in the implementation of car-reduced or car-free residential complexes, where private vehicle ownership is limited or entirely prohibited. According to Bauer et al. (2022) the core element of IMCs is the reduction of the car parking space ratio. Furthermore, IMCs aim at improving housing affordability, environmental sustainability, and urban quality of life (Küchel et al., 2024). For housing developers, IMCs can be financially attractive since they can save money by providing less parking space (Bauer et al., 2022; Topp, 2017). Successful implementation of IMCs requires a balance of restrictions and incentives tailored to the spatial (e.g., urban density, public transport availability etc.) and sociodemographic context of the residential complex, as well as political and community support (Küchel et al., 2024).

Well-known successes, such as the Vauban project in Freiburg/Breisgau (Germany) are contrasted by unsuccessful counterexamples in Germany including projects like Bremen Hollerland and Kassel Unterneustadt which struggled due to poor planning and increased parking pressure, demonstrating the challenges of applying IMCs without proper support and adaptation (Küchel et al., 2024).

The academic research on IMCs remains quite limited and narrowly focused, resulting in a substantial knowledge gap regarding their effectiveness in both urban and suburban settings. Furthermore, there is significant uncertainty about the core impacts of IMCs on residents' mobility behavior. This lack of empirical studies and quantitative data has motivated our study, which seeks to address these critical gaps and contribute to the growing body of research on IMCs in residential complexes and their influence on mobility patterns.

Thus, our study aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of how IMCs affect residents' travel behavior compare to residents of residential complexes without IMCs, exploring the overarching question: How do integrated mobility concepts in residential complexes influence residents' mobility behavior?

This paper draws primarily on data analysis from our quantitative survey, conducted between April 24, 2023, and July 17, 2023, among adult residents of 19 urban and suburban residential complexes in the German-speaking region of Switzerland. Of these, 10 complexes had implemented an IMC, while 9 had not, enabling a comparative examination of integrated mobility concepts based on a total sample of 911 valid responses. This survey stands out from previous studies not only due to its comprehensive methodology and diverse data collection but also because it allowed for the generation of detailed modal splits for each resident through the use of the travel diary methodology. To the best of the authors' knowledge, this paper is the first to thoroughly contrast the mobility behavior of residents in IMC and non-IMC (NIMC) residential complexes.

Our findings show that IMCs can significantly impact mobility behavior, particularly in urban areas. Residents of IMC complexes demonstrate lower car ownership and reduced reliance on PMT compared to those in NIMC complexes. Specifically, urban IMC residents make significantly fewer trips by PMT, with a modal share of just 9 %, compared to 17 % in NIMC complexes. Furthermore, car ownership in urban IMC households is significantly lower, with 0.36 cars per household compared to 0.59 in NIMC complexes. However, it is important to note that our survey data on residential choice factors and political attitudes indicate a noticeable effect of

self-selection.

Multivariate Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression analyses with backward elimination techniques as well as the complementary use of machine learning models, including Random Forest and Lasso Regression, reveal that the parking ratio (the availability of parking spaces) is the key factor in IMCs influencing both car ownership and PMT use. The lower the parking ratio, the greater the reduction in car use, with parking availability emerging as the strongest predictor of car dependency across the models. The study also highlights the heterogeneity of resident groups in terms of how IMCs influence mobility behavior.

After introducing the topic and key findings, [Section 2](#) reviews literature on IMCs and their impact on mobility behaviors. [Section 3](#) outlines the methodology, including survey design and statistical analysis methods. [Section 4](#) presents results, particularly focusing on factors influencing PMT mode share and car ownership. [Section 5](#) discusses findings, policy implications, and limitations. [Section 6](#) concludes with key contributions and future research suggestions.

2. Literature review and hypotheses development

Hitherto, the literature lacks uniform standards or definitions for IMCs' planning scope and content ([Blachnik, 2021](#)). While the German term "Integriertes Mobilitätskonzept" is at this point relatively well-established in the German-speaking countries of Europe (predominantly Germany, Switzerland, Austria), the term "Integrated Mobility Concept" is not as firmly established in English publications. Here, one finds related literature relating to the terms car-free or car-reduced neighborhoods ([Bachmaier & Chou, 2022](#)). In the Dutch context, often the term "autoluw" is used to describe this concept of car-free settlements ([van der Lee, 2024](#)). In Sweden, "bilfritt boende" is used to describe the concept involving both push and pull measures to foster sustainable mobility ([Arnehed, 2019](#); [Koglin et al., 2019](#)). A review of the literature suggests that while terminologies vary across languages and regions, the underlying principles, strategies, and policy measures largely overlap, supporting their functional synonymy.

In line with principles of the sustainable mobility paradigm (cf. e.g., [Banister \(2008\)](#)), IMCs pursue the objective of integrating efficient land use orientated urban development and transport planning as well as the operative approach of combining restrictive (push) and incentive-based (pull) measures to support car independency ([Ammoser & Hoppe, 2006](#); [Heldt et al., 2021](#)).

Push measures are defined as restrictive policies aimed at reducing car use by increasing costs, limiting availability, or implementing regulatory constraints. Examples include reducing parking spaces, introducing higher parking fees, congestion pricing, or implementing urban access restrictions ([Hekler et al., 2022](#)). These measures discourage car use by making it less convenient or more expensive.

In contrast, pull measures are incentive-based strategies designed to encourage sustainable mobility by making alternatives more attractive. These measures include improved public transport services, expanded cycling infrastructure, shared mobility services, or subsidies for public transport passes ([Hekler et al., 2022](#); [Meyer, 1999](#)). The effectiveness of pull measures largely depends on user acceptance and behavioral adaptation rather than direct enforcement.

However, the effectiveness of these measures is often undermined by policy inconsistencies and lack of political will. [Hekler et al. \(2022\)](#) found that in Germany, despite scientific consensus on the necessity of integrating both push and pull measures, policymakers favor incentive-based policies (pull) while avoiding restrictive measures (push) due to concerns over public opposition. This imbalance has led to limited modal shifts, as seen in the short-lived effects of the 9-Euro-Ticket policy, which increased public transport use but failed to discourage car trips due to simultaneous subsidies for fuel prices.

The German experience aligns with findings from international studies, where cities that successfully implemented push-and-pull strategies (e.g., London's congestion pricing, Stockholm's urban tolls, and Zurich's parking regulations) saw significant reductions in car use and increased adoption of sustainable transport ([Buehler et al., 2017](#); [Meyer, 1999](#)). These findings show the importance of complementary policy designs rather than isolated interventions.

Typical push and pull measures implemented in IMC residential complexes are limited car parking spaces, improvements of public transport, provisions of shared mobility services, and mixed land uses ([Blees et al., 2023](#); [Heldt & Oostendorp, 2021](#); [Heldt et al., 2021](#); [Oostendorp et al., 2020](#); [Selzer & Lanzendorf, 2022](#)).

Since the 1990s, in Western Europe, there is growing interest in car-reduced neighborhoods, but the actual implementation of such housing plans remains limited and modest in scale ([Baehler & Rérat, 2020a](#); [Schröder & Klinger, 2024](#); [Selzer & Lanzendorf, 2022](#)). In their stakeholder survey conducted in German cities, [Heldt et al. \(2021\)](#) reported that public authorities considered major challenges in the realization of IMCs in residential complexes to be foremost a lack of goodwill and the strong need for coordination, while real estate experts pointed out the ambiguous legal framework and high costs.

In Switzerland, the implementation of mobility concepts is shaped by a complex legal and regulatory framework. Cantons and municipalities are mandated to develop land-use plans that govern the spatial distribution of residential areas, commercial establishments, and recreational facilities ([DETEC, 2013](#)). To enhance coordination between different transport modes, municipalities establish dedicated mobility strategies that integrate public transport, pedestrian and cycling infrastructure, and road networks ([Stadt Luzern, 2024](#)). A key regulatory instrument in this context is parking space management, which defines minimum or maximum parking requirements per residential unit to influence mobility behavior ([Stadt Zürich, 2024](#)). These planning instruments enable authorities to impose specific mobility-related requirements on new housing developments ([Luzernmobil, 2024](#)), with investors being obliged to submit a mobility concept as part of the planning approval process. Furthermore, certain municipalities allocate building land to housing cooperatives under the condition that they develop low-car or car-free residential areas, thereby fostering sustainable urban mobility ([Stadt Luzern, 2019](#)). The availability of financial support instruments varies by municipality, facilitating the implementation of pull measures such as the installation of e-charging stations in residential areas or the provision of shared mobility services ([Kanton Luzern, 2025](#)).

To better illustrate how IMCs influence residents’ travel behavior, we present a conceptual framework in Fig. 1 that synthesizes key theoretical constructs discussed in the literature. This framework outlines the interplay between IMC policy measures, contextual factors, and behavioral outcomes. It highlights how restrictive push and incentive-based pull measures interact with residents’ socioeconomic characteristics, mobility preferences, and the built environment to shape travel behavior. Additionally, it acknowledges the potential role of self-selection effects, where individuals predisposed toward sustainable mobility choices are more likely to reside in IMC-equipped residential complexes. The framework serves as the foundation for the empirical analysis in this study, and indicates which of our hypotheses outlined hereafter relate to which factors and variables.

The most critical gap in the literature and focus of our paper concerns the empirical analysis of the impact of mobility concepts in urban residential complexes on residents’ mobility behavior. A key metric for assessing this impact is the trip-based modal split and the mode share of motorized private transport (PMT). The PMT mode share should ideally be as low as possible. However, due to the demanding methodological requirements for collecting valid modal split data, this metric is rarely addressed in existing studies. A recent elaborate publication (Küchel et al., 2024) on IMCs used this approach and centered its analyses around IMC impacts on the trip-based modal split. Understanding the impact is of paramount practical relevance, as urban and municipal planning increasingly relies on IMC to mitigate negative effects such as emissions, noise, and traffic congestion. Aumann et al. (2023) analyzed thirteen studies on IMCs in residential complexes and found that the quality of these studies is compromised by small sample sizes, the absence of comparison with complexes without IMCs, and the failure to control for relevant covariates such as demographic factors, spatial typology, or vehicle ownership when assessing impact effects. Additionally, Baehler and Rérat (2020a) highlight the scarcity of research on how car-free households cope with the absence of a private car in a predominantly car-centric society (Lagrell et al., 2018; Sattlegger & Rau, 2016). The existing, yet methodological limited findings can be summarized as follows: De Gruyter (2017) demonstrated that the average weekday mode share for car driver trips was 14 percentage points lower in IMC complexes (case sites) compared to similar developments without IMCs (control sites). Nobis (2003) compared the public transport modal share for leisure trips among residents of the car-reduced Vauban settlement in Germany, finding a trip-based share of 28 % for car-owning households versus 11 % for households without a car. In their review, De Gruyter et al. (2015) concluded that empirical evidence on the impact of IMCs on modal split varies considerably across studies, with most reporting a reduction in car driver trips of 10 to 20 percentage points.

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework for the Influence of IMCs on Residents’ Travel Behavior.

However, these evaluations often lack rigor, resulting in a significant shortage of robust evidence. Given this background, we propose to scrutinize the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis 1: The presence of an IMC is negatively correlated with the trip-based PMT mode share.

A second gap exists in the analysis of the influence of IMC on the total transport volume per person and week across all modes of transport. Like the modal shares, this indicator is also time-consuming to collect. However, it is important in terms of calculating emissions and the burden on infrastructure. The literature on the ‘city of short distances’ (Khavarian-Garmsir et al., 2023) which is a related concept to IMC, assumes that the density of services around the settlement makes journeys unnecessary and thus reduces passenger kilometers (PKM). It is assumed that poor settlement quality results in increased travel, the so-called “escape hypothesis” (Schlich et al., 2004), while the availability of good local amenities (e.g., supermarkets, healthcare, gyms, etc.) reduces the motivation for traffic-generating activities. It is disputed whether this traffic-reducing effect also applies to leisure mobility and tourism. A study by Ornetzeder et al. (2008) comparing two complexes with and without a mobility concept showed a lower total traffic volume per person and lower transport-related carbon footprint.

Other studies conclude that the influence of urban settlement structures on the distances travelled by leisure and holiday traffic has a positive effect (Schad et al., 2020; Scheffler & Heinen, 2024). It is therefore important to monitor overall transport demand with regard to possible rebound effects. As a case study of residents in the car-free Burgunder settlement in Bern shows, their consumption of energy for everyday journeys is very low, but only average for non-routine travelling (Bürgi & Hari, 2013). These contradictory results in the literature, motivate our second hypothesis:

Hypothesis 2: *An IMC correlates negatively with the total passenger kilometers of residents.*

A third gap revolves around the effect of IMCs on car ownership and the rate of car-free households (Baehler & Rérat, 2020a). The academic literature has focused on the goal of reducing car dependency (Okraszewska et al., 2024; Schröder & Klinger, 2024; Selzer & Lanzendorf, 2022). Sprei et al. (2020) conclude that car ownership is the most important variable for the choice of transport mode, i.e., those who own a car also use it. McAslan and Sprei (2023) used data from government-mandated Minimum Parking Requirements (MPR) in Swedish municipalities and found a significant positive correlation between MPR and car ownership. The study by McAslan and Sprei (2023) quantifies the impact of car ownership on private motorized transport passenger kilometers (PMT-PKM). Based on the motorization rate in fifty-six Swedish municipalities, they identified a strong relationship between kilometers traveled and car ownership.

However, the parking ratios discussed in these studies are higher than those targeted in IMC residential complexes. Thus, we posit the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis 3: *An IMC correlates negatively with the car ownership rate per household.*

A fourth gap is the lack of knowledge about which IMC measures are effective in reducing the dependent variables. While there is relative agreement in the literature that the parking space ratio is a key lever to reduce car ownership, opinions differ on the relevance of pull measures.

Based on reviewing literature on car-free and low-car developments in Europe and UK, Melia (2014) suggested that the combination of push and pull transport planning measures tends to be most effective. Selzer and Lanzendorf (2022) argued that promoting a shift from car use to sustainable mobility requires an integrated approach, combining low-car housing developments with accessible and attractive alternatives to car travel. This system would encourage residents to adopt more sustainable modes of transport. The meta analysis by Okraszewska et al. (2024) quantified the effects of transport interventions aiming at reducing car use, while findings support the viewpoint show that mixed interventions exhibit a higher rate of car use reduction in comparison with isolated push or pull interventions.

The studies reviewed in publications by Okraszewska et al. (2024) and Scheepers et al. (2014), however, did not cover the context of car-free or car-reduced residential complexes/housing developments as in our paper. Previous studies on car-reduced neighborhoods show that separating parking from residential areas (a pull measure) effectively reduces car dependence and encourages the use of alternative mobility options like public transport, bicycles, and shared mobility services (Nobis, 2003). Based on the findings of the literature, we hypothesize:

Hypothesis 4: *Restrictive (“push”) IMC measures exert a larger reducing impact on PMT mode share than incentivizing (“pull”) measures in IMCs.*

A fifth open issue revolves around the question of whether IMCs have a heterogeneous effect on the residents’ mobility behavior. Previous studies tend to focus on either spatial and structural influences or individual and socio-cultural influences on travel behavior (Selzer & Lanzendorf, 2022). Spatial context (built environment) such as close proximity to daily facilities and accessibility to alternative mobility solutions (e.g., bike sharing) play a key role in residents’ adoption of these modes (Baehler & Rérat, 2020a; Melia, 2014; Selzer & Lanzendorf, 2022). Additionally, competences and skills to use those alternatives (e.g., operation of reservation phone apps) are also important. For example, planning a multimodal trip of walking/biking and public transport requires knowledge on the public transport network (Baehler & Rérat, 2020a, 2020b; Selzer & Lanzendorf, 2022). Living longer in car-reduced residential complexes increases acceptance of car-free behavior. Older adults tend to prefer public transport over cycling or driving (Selzer & Lanzendorf, 2022). The literature on car-reduced and car-free living arrangements, however, suggests that only the non-availability of a private car is an effective means of changing mobility behavior (Nobis, 2003). The literature on car-reduced and car-free living arrangements suggests that the non-availability of a private car is an effective means of changing mobility behavior (Aumann et al., 2023; Basu & Ferreira, 2020).

However, more recent research suggests that while reduced car access remains a crucial factor, a combination of restrictive measures (push) and incentives (pull) is often necessary to effectively encourage long-term shifts toward sustainable mobility (Melia, 2014; Okraszewska et al., 2024; Schröder & Klinger, 2024). The success of such approaches depends on a range of factors, including

urban density, public transport quality, and residents' pre-existing mobility habits.

Therefore, it is assumed that IMCs are unlikely to significantly influence the mobility behavior of residents who have access to a private car and parking space. This is further supported by the fact that IMCs do not include measures such as mobility pricing, which provide sustained incentives to avoid car use. Based on these considerations, we want to substantiate the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis 5: The effectiveness of IMCs on PMT mode share depends on the heterogeneity of resident groups concerning their car ownership and residential spatial type.

Another research question concerns whether IMC complexes function successfully primarily because they attract residents who already lead car-light lifestyles and seek to reinforce their orientation and actions. Residents of car-free housing developments seem to prioritize social and ecological values in their choice of not owning a car (Baehler & Rérat, 2020a; Bles et al., 2023). This suggests that these settlements bring together a milieu that also shares immaterial aspects, such as the social, cultural, political, and economic contexts, which play a significant role in mobility. Therefore, settlements with an IMC could be understood as sites for specific "mobility cultures" (Kellerman, 2012; Klinger et al., 2013). This phenomenon is referred to as self-selection, potentially contributing to the observed lower rates of car use (Broaddus, 2010; Melia, 2014). For example, Melia et al. (2013) found that potential demand for car-free housing in the United Kingdom is concentrated among "car-free choosers" – those living without a car by choice – who are more likely to be younger, living in single-person households, and located in inner-city areas.

However, despite the potential for self-selection in car-reduced developments, the extent to which it contributes to lower rates of car use has yet to be quantified. Therefore, we hypothesize:

Hypothesis 6: *The political attitudes towards mobility and environmental issues as well as the reasons for choosing a place of residence differ significantly between residents of IMC and NIMC residential complexes.*

Heldt et al. (2021) point out that the interests of stakeholders in the implementation of IMCs are inconsistent. While investors aim to increase the attractiveness of their developments for residents, with good parking conditions being a crucial factor, the interests of municipalities and planners lie in reducing traffic volumes. Nobis (2003) reports that residents of the Vauban complex (Freiburg/Breisgau) struggle significantly with the requirement to park their cars in a central parking garage rather than directly in front of their homes. Also, Roukouni and Cats (2024) report a negative public response to low-car interventions in Amsterdam. A major challenge, therefore, is the lack of acceptance of these measures (Dieplinger & Kummer, 2014).

Since Nieuwenhuijsen (2020), Noordegraaf et al. (2014), and Kiba-Janiak and Witkowski (2019) emphasize the importance of citizen participation and the involvement of other stakeholder groups for successful IMC implementation, the question arises as to what limitations residents perceive due to these IMCs and how they subjectively assess the effects of the measures. Therefore, we propose the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis 7: Residents of IMC complexes perceive IMCs as a relevant restriction of freedom and therefore they are less likely to adopt more sustainable mobility behavior.

3. Methodology

Our study draws on the results of a mixed-method research project involving a variety of stakeholders. The theoretical framework is based on the factors known from the literature to influence mobility behavior with a focus on the choice of transport mode. Many of the survey items were inspired by established travel surveys, first and foremost the Swiss Mobility and Transport Microcensus questionnaire (FSO, 2023a).

Variables were collected for an array of dimensions. This included, for instance, variables describing the built environment and density (spatial types) as well as public transport access quality. Then, ownership of or access to transport tools such as cars, bicycles, public transport subscriptions or sharing services was surveyed. Variables such as income, family situation and employment status were collected to determine the socio-economic situation. The survey also asked attitudes and opinions towards the promotion of public transport, private motorized transport and active travel, as well as the attitudes towards the introduction of a possible CO₂ tax. We also surveyed the residents regarding the importance of several residential choice factors such as good parking availability or accessibility by public transport. Finally, a comprehensive list was used to check which measures typical for IMCs had been implemented in the individual residential complexes.

3.1. Data collection

In a first stage, we conducted 14 structured interviews with key stakeholders, including municipal officials, property owners, and private sector representatives. The interviews helped explore the planning, implementation, and evaluation of IMCs. Participants were selected based on their expertise and involvement in relevant projects. The interviews utilized a standardized set of questions, allowing for discussions with key stakeholders while ensuring consistency across interview sessions. Data were systematically analyzed to identify key insights and gain an overview of the residential complexes' characteristics, especially their IMCs and mobility-related measures and infrastructure. The IMC related measures in the residential complexes are detailed in Table 1. Furthermore, a detailed description of an exemplary residential complex with IMC is provided in Appendix A1.

The empirical centerpiece of our study is a comprehensive anonymous quantitative survey of residents aged 18 and older in 19 selected residential complexes, 9 with an IMC and 10 without (for location, see Fig. 2). The survey, available in paper and online (via Unipark) formats, ran in two waves from April 24 to July 17, 2023 including one reminder to previously invited residents. To cater to diverse demographics, it was offered in German and English, though the bilingual option was limited to the online survey. Internal pretests ensured the correction of any typographical, linguistic, and content errors. The full address data of the residents of each

Table 1
Overview of Mobility-Related Measures in Residential Complexes.

No*	IMC	PUSH MEASURES				PULL MEASURES						
		Parking ratio	Ban on PMT	Mobility monitoring	Parking Costs in CHF (Month)	Mobility vouchers	Bike-sharing/e-scooter-sharing services	Cargo bike sharing	Car-sharing services	Sustainable mobility vision	Mobility manager/center	Mobility information/workshops
1	YES	0.02	1	1	N/A	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
2	YES	0.11	1	0	150	0	0	1	1	0	0	1
3	YES	0.4	0	1	495	1	0	0	0	0	1	0
4	YES	0.63	0	1	180	1	1	1	1	0	0	1
5	YES	0.13	1	1	182.5	1	0	0	0	1	0	1
6	YES	1.27	0	0	167.5	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
7	YES	0.58	0	1	170	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
8	YES	0.26	0	1	160	0	1	1	1	0	1	1
9	YES	0.53	0	0	142.5	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
10	NO	1.6	0	0	130	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11	NO	0	0	0	N/A	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
12	NO	1.27	0	0	140	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
13	NO	0.99	0	0	160	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
14	NO	1.23	0	0	120	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
15	NO	0.17	0	0	300	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
16	NO	1.46	0	0	140	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
17	NO	0.90	1	0	150	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
18	NO	0.99	1	0	160	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
19	NO	0.72	0	0	95	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ø	N/A	0.7	0.26	0.32	179	0.21	0.17	0.26	0.44	0.16	0.16	0.37

*1) Burgunder, 2) Erlenmatt Ost, 3) Europaallee, 4) Guggachpark, 5) Kalkbreite, 6) Kunz Areal, 7) Matteo Mattenhof, 8) mehr als wohnen, 9) MinMax, 10) EBG, 11) Eichrüti, 12) Gartenhof, 13) Hof Lilienthal, 14) im Vieri, 15) Meret-Oppenheim, 16) Parkallee, 17) Siedlung Klee, 18) Tribschenstadt, 19) WG 1943 Jakobsberg.

Fig. 2. Locations of Surveyed Residential Complexes (Background Map: swisstopo, ARE).

residential complex were obtained via requests to the municipal governments. The residents were invited via personalized letters with unique alphanumeric codes for response tracking, with addresses obtained from public authorities following data protection guidelines. In the residential complex “Im Vieri”, personal invitations were not feasible. Thus, 200 random codes were distributed in this case. In complexes with fewer than 300 eligible residents (≥ 18 years of age), all were invited. In larger complexes, a random sample of 200 residents was selected to minimize bias.

To encourage participation, respondents received a 10 CHF online voucher for the Swiss national railway (SBB) upon fully completing the survey. The questionnaire covered several sections, i.e., language selection, vehicle ownership, employment and

Table 2
Survey Response Rates.

No	Name	IMC	Postal Code/City	Residents (≥ 18 years)	Surveyed Residents	Valid Responses (n)	Response Rate (%)
1	Burgunder	YES	3018 Bern	125	125	55	44.0
2	Erlenmatt Ost	YES	4058 Basel	157	157	19	12.1
3	Europaallee	YES	8004 Zürich	70	70	16	22.9
4	Guggachpark	YES	8057 Zürich	200	200	37	18.5
5	Kalkbreite	YES	8003 Zürich	184	184	48	26.1
6	Kunz Areal	YES	5210 Windisch	286	286	93	32.5
7	Matteo Mattenhof	YES	6010 Kriens	199	199	65	32.7
8	mehr als wohnen	YES	8050 Zürich	200	200	61	30.5
9	MinMax	YES	8152 Glattpark (Opfikon)	111	111	16	14.4
10	EBG	NO	3008 Bern	478	200	71	35.5
11	Eichrüti	NO	6333 Hünenberg See	342	200	43	21.5
12	Gartenhof	NO	8408 Winterthur	186	186	38	20.4
13	Hof Lilienthal	NO	8152 Glattpark (Opfikon)	179	179	43	24.0
14	im Vieri	NO	8603 Schwerzenbach	200	200	30	15.0
15	Meret-Oppenheim	NO	4053 Basel	186	186	66	35.5
16	Parkallee	NO	4123 Allschwil	224	224	42	18.8
17	Siedlung Klee	NO	8046 Zürich	200	200	31	15.5
18	Tribtschenstadt	NO	6005 Luzern	179	179	73	40.8
19	WG 1943 Jakobsberg	NO	4059 Basel	230	230	64	27.8
			Total	3'936	3'516	911	25.9

commuting patterns, a travel diary, residential satisfaction, awareness and satisfaction with mobility concepts, transportation policy attitudes, and sociodemographic information (for a detailed overview, please see the codebook to be found in the supplementary material). The centerpiece of the survey was the three-day travel diary asking residents to report on their travels for the past Monday, Wednesday and Saturday (see [Figure A2 in Appendix A1](#)). Travel diaries are a traditional but also challenging method for data collection in present times ([Prelicean et al., 2018](#); [Stopher, 1992](#)). The method has recently also been used in the context of studying mobility behavior of residents in a car-reduced neighborhood in Darmstadt, Germany ([Stete & Bonin, 2024](#)).

The survey data were supplemented with residential complex descriptions and secondary data for comprehensive analysis.

The survey was mailed to 3516 individuals across the 19 selected residential complexes. Out of the distributed surveys, 911 completed questionnaires were returned (301 on paper, 610 online), resulting in an overall response rate of 25.9 % (see [Table 2](#)), which is acceptable yet lower than the mean response rate of 44 % in online surveys in published research ([Wu et al., 2022](#)).

To enhance our primary data, we consulted several external data sources. To apply a binary spatial categorization to the residential complexes' locations into "urban" and "suburban", we drew on the official Federal Office for Spatial Development (ARE) typology of municipalities ([ARE, 2024](#)). Furthermore, to assign a public transport accessibility index to the residential complexes, we used ARE's public transport quality categories (German "ÖV Güteklassen") ([Aberegg, 2010](#)), which provide a classification framework that evaluates the quality and accessibility of public transportation in Switzerland. It assesses factors such as the proximity to public transport stops, frequency of service, and overall service quality, including punctuality, comfort, and network coverage. The system categorizes areas into five classes, ranging from A (excellent service) to E (poor or no service), helping to show the level of public transport provision. It must be noted that our residential complex sample contained no complexes located in any class worse than C.

3.2. Data analysis

Given the hybrid nature of the survey, which involved significant manual data entry, there was potential for occasional transmission errors. To mitigate this, internal controls were sporadically implemented to ensure the error rate remained within acceptable limits during the transfer of responses into the digital database. One specific challenge was the incorrect entry of alphanumeric survey IDs by 55 participants. These errors often stemmed from homoglyph confusion, where characters such as '1' and lowercase 'l', or '0' (zero) and 'O' were mistaken for each other. To address this, the Levenshtein distance algorithm was employed, comparing the erroneous IDs to the correct set of distributed codes.

To further ensure data quality, responses were cross-checked for plausibility. Although some extreme values, such as unusually high or low daily travel distances, were detected, none were deemed implausible upon review, so all data were retained for analysis. Additionally, the dataset was supplemented with secondary data, such as calculated walking, cycling, and PMT travel times to the nearest grocery stores from residential addresses, to support specific analyses (e.g., weekly total distances, binary classification of urban vs. suburban areas). Several calculated variables and dummy variables were created to facilitate these analyses.

To simplify the representation of modal split statistics, transport modes were aggregated into the broader categories Private Motorized Transport (PMT), Public Transport (PT), and Active Travel (AT) (see [Table 3](#)). Similarly, to distinguish between residential complexes and their spatial types, a dichotomous classification (urban vs. suburban) was adopted, based on the ARE typology. We classified residential complexes located in "Grosszentren" ("Big Centers") as urban, and the remainder as suburban. This classification was justified as no complexes were in areas ARE classifies as rural.

Our statistical analyses aimed to primarily investigate how IMCs influence travel behavior, with a focus on reducing car ownership and car use (PMT mode share). The analysis combined descriptive statistics, inferential tests, and advanced modeling techniques to provide a comprehensive understanding of the data.

First, descriptive statistics were used to summarize key variables such as household car ownership, public transport subscriptions, and weekly travel distances. This provided an initial comparison between residents of IMC and NIMC complexes across urban and suburban settings, offering insights into socio-demographic patterns and mobility behavior.

To identify significant differences between IMC and NIMC groups, we conducted independent sample t-tests. These tests assessed whether key outcomes, such as travel distances and ownership of mobility tools, differed significantly between the groups. This formed the foundation for exploring the impact of IMCs on travel behavior.

Next, Random Forest ([Breiman, 2001](#)) and Lasso regression ([Tibshirani, 1996](#)) were employed to examine which IMC factors most strongly predicted PMT mode share. The Random Forest method provided a ranking of variable importance, identifying key predictors

Table 3
Aggregation of Modes of Transport.

jlh	Aggregated Mode of Transport	Abbreviation
Car with Internal Combustion Engine (Diesel, Gasoline, LPG/CNG)	Private Motorized Transport	PMT
Electric Car / (Plug-In) Hybrid Car		
Motorcycle / Motorbike / Scooter		
Bicycle	Active Travel	AT
E-Bike / E-Cargo Bike (electric cargo bicycle)		
(E-)Scooter / (E-)Kick Scooter	Public Transport	PT
On Foot (from 5 min walking time)		
Local Public Transport		
Public Transport (Public Transit)		

such as parking availability, car ownership, and access to public transport. Lasso regression, a form of regularized regression, was used to refine the model by applying a penalty to the size of the regression coefficients. This technique helps to prevent overfitting by discouraging the model from assigning too much importance to less relevant variables. Unlike traditional regression, Lasso adds a constraint to the optimization process by penalizing the absolute size of the coefficients, which leads to some coefficients being shrunk to exactly zero.

The final analysis used multivariate Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression to quantify the effects of these key factors on PMT mode share. The dependent variable, PMT mode share, represented the proportion of trips made by PMT over a week. Independent variables included mobility tool ownership, IMC measures, demographic information (e.g., household income, age, gender, etc.), spatial context, public transport quality, political attitudes and residential choice factors (for a detailed account of the independent variables, please refer to [Table 4](#)). Using Python, the OLS model was refined through the backward elimination technique (cf. e.g., [Halinski and Feldt \(1970\)](#)), systematically removing variables with higher p-values until only significant predictors remained. Multicollinearity was addressed using the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) (see e.g., [O'Brien \(2007\)](#)) to ensure that variables did not overly influence each other.

In addition to OLS, Ridge and Lasso regressions were applied to handle multicollinearity and improve the stability of the model. Ridge regression shrinks coefficients without setting any to zero, while Lasso can eliminate irrelevant variables entirely. Both methods helped confirm the importance of parking availability and car ownership in determining PMT use.

To validate the models, the dataset was split into training and test sets. The models were trained on the training set and evaluated on the test set using Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) as the performance metric, ensuring the models' predictive accuracy. While Ridge regression showed slightly better performance in predictive terms, the OLS model provided clear, interpretable results on how variables like parking ratio and car ownership influence PMT mode share.

4. Results

This chapter presents the findings from our analysis of IMCs and their effects on travel behavior. It explores differences in travel metrics such as car use and ownership, and daily travel distances between residents of IMC and NIMC complexes. The analysis distinguishes between urban and suburban settings, using statistical methods to reveal how IMCs influence mobility behavior.

4.1. Household demographics

Based on our survey, socio-economic data of 911 residents is available for households in the 19 studied residential complexes, both with and without mobility concepts (See [Table 5](#)). The respondents' median age of 44 years is slightly below the Swiss median (45.9 years) ([FSO, 2024a](#)), and the mean household income of CHF 9900 is comparable to the Swiss average of CHF 9780 ([FSO, 2024b](#)).

No systematic differences between complexes with and without mobility concepts were found for either of these indicators. Deviating from the Swiss average, the study revealed a high proportion of residents (72.1 %) with a tertiary education compared to the Swiss average of 44 % ([FSO, 2021](#)). This overrepresentation of highly educated individuals in car-reduced and car-free residential complexes in Switzerland aligns with findings from previous studies ([Baehler & Rérat, 2020a, 2020b](#)). Given that this educational skew is a known structural characteristic rather than a sampling artifact, applying statistical weights would not meaningfully correct for bias.

Regarding educational backgrounds one can clearly see that the proportion of highly educated (tertiary education) people in our IMC complex sample is significantly higher (76 %) compared to NIMC complexes (68 %). In contrast, the proportion of people with apprenticeships/vocational training background is noticeably higher in NIMC complexes (23 %), compared to IMC complexes (15 %). The employment rate of 80.3 % in our sample is as high as the Swiss average of 80.3 % ([Trading Economics, 2024](#)).

Furthermore, residents were asked about their awareness of a mobility concept in their residential complex. Results showed that in residential complexes without an IMC, 29 % of respondents erroneously assumed the existence of an IMC in their residential complex. In contrast, in complexes that had an IMC, between 2 % and 19 % (overall mean of 8 %) of respondents did not believe an IMC existed, and between 2 % and 38 % (overall mean of 13 %) were not sure whether an IMC existed in their residential complex.

4.2. Political opinions and residential choice factors of residents

The group comparison results highlight clear distinctions in political opinions and residential preferences between residents of urban and suburban complexes, particularly when comparing IMC and NIMC complexes.

In urban areas, IMC residents showed significantly stronger support for public transportation, with a mean score of 4.52 compared to 4.32 for NIMC residents ($p = 0.002$). Urban IMC residents also favored improvements in walking and cycling infrastructure more strongly, scoring 4.58 versus 4.28 for NIMC residents ($p < 0.001$). These results suggest that residents of IMC environments tend to favor sustainable mobility options, likely reflecting the mobility features integrated into these complexes. On the other hand, urban NIMC residents placed a higher priority on road traffic improvements (3.10 vs. 2.63, $p < 0.001$) and good parking availability (2.46 vs. 1.94, $p < 0.001$). These preferences suggest a greater reliance on personal vehicles among urban NIMC residents, who seem to prioritize car-friendly infrastructure over sustainable alternatives.

In suburban areas, the differences between IMC and NIMC residents were less noticeable but still significant in key areas. Suburban NIMC residents placed significantly greater importance on good parking availability (3.07 vs. 2.77, $p = 0.033$). A difference in suburban areas was the preference for shared mobility options, where IMC residents placed more emphasis on the availability of such

Table 4
Summary of Modeling Approach/Variables.

Cat.	Subcat.	Variable Name (Translated from German Survey)	Type ^a	Description	Data Source	
Dependent Variable		Total PMT Mode Share (Whole Week)	Cont.	Private Motorized Transport Mode Share (Entire Week, Trip-Based) (Values 0–1)	Survey (Travel Diary Part)	
Independent Variables	Mobility Tool Ownership	Car Ownership	Disc.	Number of Cars (0, 1, 2,...) in Household	Survey	
		E-Bike Ownership	Disc.	Number of E-Bikes (0, 1, 2,...) in Household	Survey	
		Normal Bike Ownership	Disc.	Number of Non-Motorized Bicycles (0, 1, 2,...) in Household	Survey	
	Spatial Type/PT Accessibility	Urban_Suburban Dummy	Cat.	Indicator for Urban or Suburban Spatial Type based on Federal Office for Spatial Planning's (ARE) Spatial Typology	Federal Office for Spatial Planning (ARE)	
		Public Transport Quality	Cat.	Quality of Public Transport in the Area (Classes: A, B, C, D, E)	Federal Office for Spatial Planning (ARE)	
	Demographics	Household Income		Cat.	Monthly Household Income Categories (1 = 4,001–6,000 CHF; 2 = 6,001–8,000 CHF; 3 = 8,001–10,000 CHF; 4 = 10,001–12,000 CHF; 5 = 12,001–14,000 CHF; 6 = 14,001–16,000 CHF; 7 = 16,001–18,000 CHF; 8 = 18,001 CHF and above; 9 = Less than 4,000 CHF)	Survey
			Age	Cont.	Age of Respondent (Calculated from Year of Birth)	Survey
			Number of Children	Cont.	Number of Children in Household (Aged 17 or below)	Survey
		Education Level		Cat.	Highest Education Level (1 = No Degree; 2 = Secondary Education; 3 = Apprenticeship; 4 = A-Levels/High School; 5 = Tertiary Education)	Survey
			Employment Status	Cat.	Dummy Variable of Employment Status (0 = Unemployed; 1 = Employed)	Survey
		Gender		Cat.	Gender of Respondent (0 = Female, 1 = Male, 2 = Undefined)	Survey
				Cat.	Gender of Respondent (0 = Female, 1 = Male, 2 = Undefined)	Survey
	PT Subscriptions	GA Travelcard (GA)		Cat.	Ownership of a SBB GA Travelcard (0 = No, 1 = Yes)	Survey
			Regional Transport Subscription	Cat.	Ownership of a Regional Travelcard (0 = No, 1 = Yes)	Survey
		Half-Fare Travelcard	Cat.	Ownership of a Half-Fare ("Halbtax") Travelcard (0 = No, 1 = Yes)	Survey	
		No Travelcard	Cat.	No Ownership of Any Public Transport Travelcard (0 = No, 1 = Yes)	Survey	
	Political Opinions	Opinion on Public Transport Promotion	Cat.	Support for Public Transport Promotion (Likert Scale 1 to 5, 1 = Fully Disagree, 5 = Fully Agree)	Survey	
		Opinion on Road Traffic Improvements	Cat.	Support for Road Traffic Improvements (Likert Scale 1 to 5, 1 = Fully Disagree, 5 = Fully Agree)	Survey	
		Opinion on Pedestrian/Bicycle Improvements	Cat.	Support for Pedestrian and Bicycle Improvements (Likert Scale 1 to 5, 1 = Fully Disagree, 5 = Fully Agree)	Survey	
Opinion on Introduction of CO2 Tax		Cat.	Support for CO2 Tax (Likert Scale 1 to 5, 1 = Fully Disagree, 5 = Fully Agree)	Survey		
Residential Choice Factors	Residential Choice: Proximity to Highway		Cat.	Proximity to Highway as a Factor in Residential Choice (Likert Scale 1 to 5, 1 = Not Important at All, 5 = Very Important; 6 = not applicable (excluded from results))	Survey	
		Residential Choice: Public Transport Accessibility	Cat.	Public Transport Accessibility as a Factor in Residential Choice (Likert Scale 1 to 5, 1 = Not Important at All, 5 = Very Important; 6 = not applicable (excluded from results))	Survey	
	Residential Choice: Proximity to Family	Cat.	Proximity to Family as a Factor in Residential Choice	Survey		
	Residential Choice: Proximity to Educational Institution	Cat.	Proximity to Educational Institution as a Factor in Residential Choice (Likert Scale 1 to 5, 1 = Not Important at All, 5 = Very Important; 6 = not applicable (excluded from results))	Survey		
	Residential Choice: Housing Availability	Cat.	Housing Availability as a Factor in Residential Choice (Likert Scale 1 to 5, 1 = Not Important at All, 5 = Very Important; 6 = not applicable (excluded from results))	Survey		
	Residential Choice: Moving due to Partner/Family	Cat.	Moving due to Partner/Family as a Factor in Residential Choice (Likert Scale 1 to 5, 1 = Not Important at All, 5 = Very Important; 6 = not applicable (excluded from results))	Survey		
	Residential Choice: Attractiveness of Housing Complex	Cat.	Attractiveness of Housing Complex as a Factor in Residential Choice (Likert Scale 1 to 5, 1 = Not	Survey		

(continued on next page)

Table 4 (continued)

Cat.	Subcat.	Variable Name (Translated from German Survey)	Type ^a	Description	Data Source
		Residential Choice: Family-Friendly Environment	Cat.	Important at All, 5 = Very Important; 6 = not applicable (excluded from results) Family-Friendly Environment as a Factor in Residential Choice (Likert Scale 1 to 5, 1 = Not Important at All, 5 = Very Important; 6 = not applicable (excluded from results))	Survey
		Residential Choice: Price-Performance Ratio of Rental Apartments	Cat.	Price-Performance Ratio of Rental Apartments as a Factor in Residential Choice (Likert Scale 1 to 5, 1 = Not Important at All, 5 = Very Important; 6 = not applicable (excluded from results))	Survey
		Residential Choice: Shared Mobility Options	Cat.	Availability of Shared Mobility Options as a Factor in Residential Choice (Likert Scale 1 to 5, 1 = Not Important at All, 5 = Very Important; 6 = not applicable (excluded from results))	Survey
		Residential Choice: Good Parking Availability	Cat.	Good Parking Availability as a Factor in Residential Choice (Likert Scale 1 to 5, 1 = Not Important at All, 5 = Very Important; 6 = not applicable (excluded from results))	Survey
		Residential Choice: Pedestrian/Bicycle-Friendly Environment	Cat.	Pedestrian/Bicycle-Friendly Environment as a Factor in Residential Choice (Likert Scale 1 to 5, 1 = Not Important at All, 5 = Very Important; 6 = not applicable (excluded from results))	Survey
	Mobility Concept Measures	Parking Ratio	Cont.	Ratio of Parking Spaces to Residential Units	Interviews with Property Managers
		PMT Ban	Cat.	Presence of a Ban on PMT in the Area (0 = No/Not available, 1 = Yes/Available)	Interviews with Property Managers
		Monthly Parking Costs for Resident Parking	Cont.	Price for a Residential Parking Spot in CHF (per Month)	Interviews with Property Managers
		Active Mobility Management	Cat.	Implementation of Active Mobility Management (0 = No/Not available, 1 = Yes/Available)	Interviews with Property Managers
		Mobility Vouchers	Cat.	Availability of Mobility Vouchers (0 = No/Not available, 1 = Yes/Available)	Interviews with Property Managers
		Bike/E-Scooter Sharing in Area	Cat.	Availability of Bike/E-Scooter Sharing in the Area (0 = No/Not available, 1 = Yes/Available)	Interviews with Property Managers
		Cargo Bike Sharing in Area	Cat.	Availability of Cargo Bike Sharing in the Area (0 = No/Not available, 1 = Yes/Available)	Interviews with Property Managers
		Micromobility Sharing in Area	Cat.	Availability of Micromobility Sharing (e.g., scooters, etc.) (0 = No/Not available, 1 = Yes/Available)	Interviews with Property Managers
		Car Sharing in Area	Cat.	Availability of Car Sharing in the Area (0 = No/Not available, 1 = Yes/Available)	Interviews with Property Managers
		Sustainable Mobility Ideal	Cat.	Presence of a Sustainable Mobility Ideal in the Area (0 = No/Not available, 1 = Yes/Available)	Interviews with Property Managers
		Mobility Manager/ Mobility Center	Cat.	Presence of a Mobility Manager or Mobility Center (0 = No/Not available, 1 = Yes/Available)	Interviews with Property Managers
		Mobility Information in Residential Complex	Cat.	Availability of Mobility Information (e.g., brochures, apps) (0 = No/Not available, 1 = Yes/Available)	Interviews with Property Managers

^a Cont. = Continuous, Cat. = Categorical, Disc. = Discrete.

solutions (2.54 vs. 2.14, $p = 0.002$), even in less dense areas where car ownership is generally more common. However, the availability of shared mobility services was not ranked as a crucial factor across the sample.

The distinction between car-owning and car-free households further illuminates differences in political and residential preferences. In both urban and suburban IMC complexes, car-free households expressed significantly stronger support for public transportation and improvements in walking and cycling infrastructure. For example, urban car-free residents in IMC complexes expressed much support (4.63) for public transport promotion, compared to 4.16 for car owners ($p < 0.001$). Similarly, car-free urban IMC residents supported walking and cycling infrastructure more strongly than car owners, with scores of 4.67 versus 4.29 ($p < 0.001$).

Table 5
Survey Sample Description.

		Residential Complex No.*																			
		Total	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19
Net Sample		911	55	19	16	37	48	93	65	61	16	71	43	38	43	30	66	42	31	73	64
IMC	Yes/No	n/a	Yes	No																	
Residents IMC Awareness	Correct (%)	55.8	85.5	57.9	81.3	78.4	89.6	67.7	84.6	95.1	43.8	12.7	72.1	63.2	11.6	56.7	22.7	38.1	3.2	32.9	64.1
	Incorrect (%)	18.5	9.1	15.8	6.3	2.7	6.3	12.9	3.1	3.3	18.8	71.8	0.0	10.5	44.2	10.0	31.8	19.0	51.6	27.4	6.3
	Uncertain (%)	25.7	5.5	26.3	12.5	18.9	4.2	19.4	12.3	1.6	37.5	15.5	27.9	26.3	44.2	33.3	45.5	42.9	45.2	39.7	29.7
Car-Free Households	Share in %	48.7	78.2	68.4	62.5	48.6	95.8	19.4	43.1	82.0	75.0	63.4	16.3	26.3	39.5	20.0	62.1	14.3	29.0	46.6	34.4
Age	Min	18	27.0	19.0	25.0	26.0	19.0	20.0	18.0	20.0	26.0	22.0	20.0	25.0	25.0	26.0	29.0	19.0	25.0	20.0	18.0
	Max	82	81.0	70.0	61.0	75.0	78.0	84.0	78.0	71.0	50.0	86.0	78.0	82.0	68.0	82.0	87.0	89.0	77.0	90.0	82.0
	Mean	45.6	48.2	28.9	38.7	36.1	52.9	47.6	36.7	41.0	34.3	52.0	45.9	46.2	37.5	42.5	46.3	48.0	46.9	49.8	54.4
	Std. Dev.	14.9	12.9	11.7	10.1	8.7	13.5	13.6	11.9	11.2	5.9	12.7	13.5	19.4	10.6	12.8	15.9	16.7	12.1	16.6	15.5
	Median	44.0	44.0	24.0	39.0	34.0	52.5	47.0	33.0	39.0	32.5	50.0	46.0	36.0	34.0	38.5	39.5	45.0	45.0	48.0	55.0
Gender	Female	47.5	50.9	57.9	6.3	37.8	54.2	47.3	47.7	44.3	37.5	47.9	44.2	52.6	53.5	50.0	36.4	52.4	48.4	56.2	50.0
Children	<6 Years (Avg.)	n/a	0.5	0.1	0.0	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.0	0.6	0.0	0.3	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.3	0.2	0.5	0.4	0.5	0.4
	6–17 Years (Avg.)	n/a	1.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.6	0.4	0.1	0.6	0.0	1.2	0.7	0.1	0.1	0.7	0.2	0.3	1.1	0.5	0.5
Highest Educational Background (%)	No Degree	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.3	0.0	2.8	0.0	2.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Secondary Education	1.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.2	2.2	1.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.8	6.5	2.7	6.3
	Apprenticeship A-Levels/High School	17.5	12.7	5.3	0.0	2.7	8.3	25.8	26.2	4.9	18.8	22.5	16.3	31.6	16.3	16.7	7.6	31.0	22.6	23.3	39.1
	Tertiary Education	8.2	1.8	42.1	6.3	8.1	8.3	1.1	10.8	6.6	6.3	4.2	14.0	5.3	4.7	3.3	3.0	9.5	9.7	6.8	4.7
Employment Status	Employed	72.1	85.5	52.6	93.8	89.2	79.2	71.0	61.5	85.2	75.0	70.4	69.8	55.3	79.1	80.0	89.4	54.8	61.3	67.1	50.0
	Retired	80.3	81.8	42.1	100	91.9	83.3	79.6	90.8	86.9	93.8	76.1	88.4	68.4	93.0	90.0	77.3	66.7	77.4	76.7	62.5
	In Education/Training	11.3	9.1	5.3	0.0	2.7	16.7	10.8	3.1	6.6	0.0	14.1	7.0	28.9	2.3	6.7	16.7	16.7	12.9	21.9	32.8
	Unemployed	10.0	3.6	73.7	6.3	5.4	4.2	9.7	12.3	14.8	6.3	5.6	9.3	2.6	9.3	3.3	1.5	4.8	3.2	6.8	7.8
Monthly Household Income Groups (%)	< 4000 CHF	1.4	5.5	0.0	0.0	2.7	0.0	1.1	1.5	3.3	6.3	1.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.3	0.0	2.4	0.0	0.0	0.0
	4,001–6,000 CHF	11.4	5.5	78.9	0.0	2.7	22.9	14.0	9.2	8.2	6.3	2.8	7.0	13.2	2.3	3.3	1.5	4.8	9.7	9.6	15.6
	6,001–8,000 CHF	11.4	16.4	5.3	0.0	5.4	22.9	9.7	7.7	11.5	25.0	7.0	4.7	13.2	14.0	6.7	4.5	9.5	12.9	20.5	18.8
	8,001–10,000 CHF	18.0	18.2	5.3	12.5	16.2	16.7	17.2	21.5	23.0	18.8	19.7	11.6	23.7	18.6	10.0	12.1	23.8	29.0	15.1	28.1
	10,001–12,000 CHF	15.3	16.4	5.3	25.0	5.4	14.6	19.4	15.4	13.1	6.3	22.5	14.0	15.8	18.6	16.7	19.7	9.5	16.1	21.9	14.1
	12,001–14,000 CHF	11.8	16.4	5.3	6.3	10.8	6.3	7.5	16.9	8.2	12.5	18.3	11.6	15.8	2.3	20.0	12.1	7.1	22.6	12.3	12.5
	14,001–16,000 CHF	9.0	16.4	0.0	6.3	10.8	4.2	9.7	12.3	8.2	6.3	12.7	9.3	5.3	7.0	6.7	10.6	23.8	6.5	9.6	4.7
	16,001–18,000 CHF	8.2	9.1	0.0	12.5	8.1	0.0	10.8	6.2	14.8	12.5	9.9	23.3	10.5	4.7	10.0	12.1	9.5	0.0	2.7	0.0
	> 18,001 CHF	3.7	0.0	0.0	6.3	10.8	2.1	2.2	9.2	8.2	0.0	1.4	4.7	0.0	9.3	0.0	6.1	4.8	0.0	0.0	4.7
Household Income (in Thousand CHF)	Mean	10.6	0.0	0.0	31.3	29.7	10.4	9.7	1.5	4.9	12.5	2.8	11.6	2.6	20.9	26.7	19.7	7.1	3.2	5.5	1.6
	Std. Dev.	9.9	9.2	4.8	13.2	13.0	8.0	9.8	9.9	10.1	9.7	10.0	11.7	8.7	11.2	12.0	12.2	10.6	8.4	8.7	7.9
	Median	4.4	3.4	2.0	4.4	4.8	4.5	4.5	4.0	4.5	4.8	3.4	4.4	3.7	5.1	4.6	4.3	4.2	3.2	3.8	3.5
		9.0	9.0	4.0	14.0	13.0	7.0	9.0	9.0	9.0	8.0	9.0	12.0	8.0	9.0	11.0	11.0	11.0	7.0	9.0	7.0

*1) Burgunder, 2) Erlenmatt Ost, 3) Europaallee, 4) Guggachpark, 5) Kalkbreite, 6) Kunz Areal, 7) Matteo Mattenhof, 8) mehr als wohnen, 9) MinMax, 10) EBG, 11) Eichrütli, 12) Gartenhof, 13) Hof Lilienthal, 14) im Vieri, 15) Meret-Oppenheim, 16) Parkallee, 17) Siedlung Klee, 18) Tribschenstadt, 19) WG 1943 Jakobsberg.

Although the differences were less statistically significant in suburban areas, the same trend persisted, indicating a consistent preference for sustainable mobility among car-free households in IMC environments. In NIMC complexes, car-free households still displayed a stronger preference for sustainable mobility than car-owning households, though the differences were less pronounced than in IMC settings. For instance, in urban NIMC complexes, car-free residents showed greater support for public transportation than car owners (3.46 vs. 2.74, $p < 0.001$), and they placed significantly less importance on good parking availability (1.81 vs. 3.09, $p < 0.001$).

Certain residential preferences, such as proximity to family, housing availability, and the price-performance ratio of rentals, did not show significant differences across groups, showing that these factors remain universally important regardless of mobility preferences. This suggests that while mobility needs shape political opinions and other residential preferences, basic housing needs such as family proximity and housing accessibility are consistently important across all resident groups. For a detailed breakdown of the results, please refer to [Table 16](#) and [Table 17](#) in [Appendix A1](#).

4.3. Mobility of residents

4.3.1. Driver's licenses and public transport subscriptions

In urban residential complexes, 81 % of residents have a driver's license, with no significant variation between IMC and NIMC complexes. In suburban areas, this rate is generally higher, reaching 87 % for IMC residents and 89 % for those in NIMC complexes, though these differences are not statistically significant. The ownership of both car and motorcycle licenses is slightly higher in suburban NIMC complexes (24 %) compared to IMC complexes (20 %), and this difference is also reflected in urban areas where NIMC residents are more likely to hold both types of licenses (23 % vs. 17 %, $p = 0.033$).

When considering PT subscriptions, significant differences emerge. In urban areas, the proportion of residents owning a GA Travelcard, which provides nationwide access to Swiss public transport, is high at 25 %, significantly above the national average of 9 % (FSO, 2023b), with no substantial difference between IMC and NIMC complexes. However, the proportion of individuals without any public transportation subscription is significantly higher in urban NIMC complexes (10 %) compared to IMC complexes (4 %, $p = 0.003$). This suggests that IMC environments may encourage greater use of public transportation by providing more integrated mobility solutions.

In suburban areas, significant differences in GA Travelcard ownership were observed. IMC residents were more likely to hold a GA Travelcard (14 %) compared to their NIMC counterparts (9 %, $p = 0.043$), while ownership of regional travelcards was also more common among NIMC residents (21 %) than IMC residents (12 %, $p = 0.011$). However, the proportion of suburban residents without a public transport subscription was consistent across both IMC and NIMC complexes, at 14 %.

These findings indicate that while driver's license possession remains stable across both urban and suburban contexts, public transport subscription patterns differ significantly, particularly in urban areas, where IMC complexes seem to foster a greater reliance on public transport. Suburban areas exhibit a more mixed picture, with GA Travelcard ownership higher among IMC residents but regional travelcard ownership more prevalent in NIMC complexes. For detailed information on the inferential statistics, please refer to [Appendix A4](#) and [Table 18](#) ([Table 6](#)).

4.3.2. Vehicle ownership

In urban residential complexes, households in IMC environments own significantly fewer cars than those in NIMC complexes, with a mean ownership rate of 0.36 cars per household in IMC compared to 0.59 in NIMC ($p < 0.001$) complexes. IMC residents also see higher electric vehicle (EV) ownership (0.06 vs. 0.03, $p = 0.048$). Although bicycle and e-bike ownership rates do not differ significantly, there is a strong variation in e-cargo bike ownership between IMC and NIMC complexes.

In suburban areas, while IMC households also own fewer cars (0.86 vs. 0.97 in NIMC), this difference is not statistically significant. However, car-free households are much more common in IMC complexes, particularly in urban settings where 76 % of households are car-free, compared to 49 % in NIMC complexes. In suburban areas, car-free households are also more prevalent in IMC complexes (58 % vs. 39 %), though not significantly different.

Both urban and suburban IMC complexes show higher car-free rates than the national average of 22 % (FSO, 2023b), highlighting the impact of IMCs in reducing car dependence. Moreover, IMC suburban households have higher EV ownership (0.10 vs. 0.02 in

Table 6
Driver's License and Public Transport Subscription Ownership.

		CH Average (2021)	Whole Sample	Urban		Suburban	
				IMC	NIMC	IMC	NIMC
Driver's License Type (Shares in %)	Car	83	84	81	81	87	89
	Motorcycle	n/a	22	17*	23*	21	26
	Both Categories	n/a	21	17*	23*	20	24
	No Driver's License	17	16	19	19	13	10
PT Subscription Type (Shares in %)	GA Travelcard	9	20	25	26	14*	9*
	Half-Fare Travelcard	35	64	66*	56*	67	69
	Regional Travelcard	11	18	17*	21*	12*	21*
	No PT Subscription	47	10	4*	10*	14	14

* = $p < 0.05$.

NIMC), indicating an inclination towards sustainable transportation options. For more details, please see [Table 7](#).

4.3.3. Traveled distances

The comparison between IMC and NIMC residents reveals significant differences in travel behavior, particularly in PT usage. Across the whole sample, IMC residents consistently traveled more by PT, especially on Saturdays (48.1 km vs. 39.6 km, $p = 0.027$) and throughout the whole week (44.4 km vs. 29.3 km, $p = 0.001$). Active transport (AT) is also higher among IMC residents across all periods, with significant differences on Saturdays (9.2 km vs. 7.2 km, $p = 0.063$) and whole week (9.2 km vs. 7.2 km, $p = 0.031$).

In urban areas, IMC residents showed significantly higher PT usage over the whole week (47.5 km vs. 30.4 km, $p = 0.017$) and Saturdays (67.8 km vs. 40.4 km, $p = 0.003$). The total distance traveled was also higher for IMC residents, particularly over the whole week (71.7 km vs. 57 km, $p = 0.035$). There were no significant differences in PMT usage between IMC and NIMC residents in urban areas.

In suburban areas, IMC residents also traveled more by PMT on weekdays (41.4 km vs. 25.4 km, $p = 0.039$) and active transport (AT), especially over the whole week (8.4 km vs. 5.3 km, $p = 0.014$). The difference in PT usage was lower, with no significant differences on weekdays or Saturdays, although a near-significant trend was observed for weekdays ($p = 0.057$).

To conclude, IMC residents, especially in urban areas, traveled significantly more by PT and engaged more in AT, while PMT usage showed a modest reduction in suburban areas but remained similar in urban contexts. For more details, please refer to [Fig. 3](#) as well as [Table 19](#) and [Table 20](#) in [Appendix A5](#).

4.3.4. Modal splits

The analysis of the trip-based and distance-based modal splits between Integrated Mobility Concepts (IMC) and Non-Integrated Mobility Concepts (NIMC) in residential complexes highlights distinct patterns in urban and suburban areas. The findings show that IMC complexes may be more effective in reducing the use of PMT and promoting PT use in urban contexts, while in suburban areas, IMCs seem to have a more limited impact on travel behavior.

In urban areas, the results show a clear and significant difference in PMT use between IMC and NIMC complexes across all time periods. For example, over the whole week (Mo-Su), residents in urban IMC complexes show a significantly lower share of PMT use compared to those in NIMC complexes, with a mean difference of -0.083 ($p < 0.001$) for trip-based modal splits. This trend holds true for weekdays (Mo-Fr) and Saturday, where PMT use is consistently lower in IMC complexes. The distance-based analysis further reinforces this finding, with significant reductions in PMT use in urban IMC complexes, especially over the whole week (mean difference = -0.117 , $p < 0.001$). These results suggest that IMCs are highly effective in reducing both the frequency and distance of car trips in urban areas, likely due to improved access to alternative mobility options and stricter parking regulations in these complexes.

In contrast, PT use in urban IMC complexes is generally higher than in NIMC complexes, though the differences are not always statistically significant for trip-based modal splits. Notably, on Saturday, PT use is higher in IMC complexes (mean difference = 0.068), approaching statistical significance ($p = 0.055$). However, the distance-based analysis shows more pronounced differences, with significant increases in PT use in IMC complexes, particularly over the whole week (mean difference = 0.087 , $p = 0.015$) and on Saturday (mean difference = 0.099 , $p = 0.010$). This shows that residents of urban IMC complexes tend to rely on public transport for longer-distance trips, particularly during weekends, when leisure travel may increase.

For AT, the differences between IMC and NIMC complexes in urban areas are less pronounced. While the trip-based results show slightly higher AT shares in IMC complexes, these differences are not statistically significant across any of the time periods. Similarly, the distance-based analysis reveals no significant differences in AT use between the two types of complexes, suggesting that the increase in active travel stays marginal, particularly for longer trips.

Moving to suburban areas, the results show that IMCs have a much more limited impact on modal splits compared to urban contexts. The t-tests reveal no significant differences in PMT use between IMC and NIMC complexes for any time period, whether

Table 7
Mobility Tool Ownership.

		Whole Sample	Urban		Suburban	
			IMC	NIMC	IMC	NIMC
Car (All Types)	Mean	0.67	0.36*	0.59*	0.86	0.97
	Std. Dev.	0.83	0.99	0.67	0.82	0.70
Electric Car	Mean	0.05	0.06*	0.03*	0.10*	0.02*
	Std. Dev.	0.25	0.33	0.18	0.32	0.12
Hybrid Car	Mean	0.05	0.05	0.03	0.05	0.08
	Std. Dev.	0.25	0.32	0.18	0.21	0.27
Motorcycle	Mean	0.11	0.08	0.10	0.13	0.13
	Std. Dev.	0.35	0.32	0.29	0.40	0.40
E-Bike	Mean	0.32	0.28	0.32	0.39	0.29
	Std. Dev.	0.65	0.62	0.63	0.67	0.70
Bicycle	Mean	1.69	1.90	1.73	1.37*	1.67*
	Std. Dev.	1.37	1.33	1.45	1.26	1.33
E-Scooter	Mean	0.11	0.08	0.11	0.08	0.15
	Std. Dev.	0.46	0.45	0.49	0.33	0.53

** = $p < 0.05$ in t-test.

Fig. 3. Comparison of Mean Daily Distances Across Various Time Intervals.

Fig. 4. Modal Split Comparisons, (** indicates $p < 0.05$).

measured on a trip-based or distance-based basis. This suggests that the structural characteristics of suburban environments, such as lower density and greater distances between destinations, make it more difficult for IMCs to reduce car dependency. The convenience of car use, combined with limited PT infrastructure, likely contributes to this persistent reliance on PMT in suburban areas.

Similarly, for PT and AT, there are no significant differences between IMC and NIMC complexes in suburban areas. Both trip-based and distance-based analyses show that residents of suburban IMC complexes are no more likely to use PT or AT than those in NIMC complexes. This implies that the availability of alternative transport options, even within the framework of an IMC, may not lead to substantial shifts away from car use in suburban contexts. The findings suggest that more comprehensive improvements to PT services and active travel infrastructure may be necessary to encourage residents of suburban complexes to reduce their reliance on cars.

The results highlight the effectiveness of IMCs in urban residential complexes, where they significantly reduce PMT use and promote PT for both short and long trips. However, in suburban residential complexes, the impact of IMCs is far less pronounced, with no significant differences in modal splits between IMC and NIMC complexes. A comprehensive summary of the modal splits, *t*-test results as well as comparative visualization of the modal splits are provided in Table 21 and Table 22 in Appendix A4, as well as Fig. 4 below.

4.3.5. Shared mobility use

IMCs typically include car-sharing and micromobility options as supply-side measures to offset the lower number of private cars and parking spaces, facilitating residents' transition to alternatives to PMT (Leeb, 2021).

It was hypothesized that residents of IMC complexes are more likely to use shared mobility services than those in areas without such mobility concepts. Our survey results (cf. Table 8) support this hypothesis, showing significantly higher usage rates in urban IMC complexes, particularly for e-bikes (mean difference = -0.457, standard error = 0.205, $p = 0.011$), e-scooters (mean difference = -0.756, standard error = 0.162, $p < 0.001$), carpooling (mean difference = -0.128, standard error = 0.072, $p = 0.022$), commercial car-sharing (mean difference = -0.508, standard error = 0.204, $p = 0.006$), and micromobility (mean difference = -1.213, standard error = 0.273, $p < 0.001$) compared to areas without IMC. These results indicate a positive correlation between IMC implementation and increased shared mobility usage in urban areas.

However, despite the statistical significance (for more details, refer to Table 23 in Appendix A7), the absolute frequency of shared service usage remains relatively low. Even among frequent users, those residing in urban IMC complexes, commercial car-sharing, private car-sharing, and micromobility services are used only about 1.5 times over a six-month period.

In suburban complexes, the use of e-bikes (mean difference = -1.139, standard error = 0.261, $p < 0.001$), commercial car-sharing (mean difference = -0.412, standard error = 0.205, $p = 0.021$), and micromobility (mean difference = -0.945, standard error = 0.306, $p < 0.001$) is also statistically significantly higher in areas with IMC compared to those without. However, there are no significant differences in the usage rates of private car-sharing ($p = 0.165$) and carpooling ($p = 0.13$) between the areas with and without IMC, regardless of spatial type.

Lastly, while shared mobility services are more frequently used by residents of IMC complexes – especially in urban settings – the actual usage rates remain low overall.

4.3.6. Self-reported impacts and awareness of IMCs

The analysis of self-reported perceptions of residents of IMC complexes concerning various aspects of how the IMC affects their life showed interesting differences between residents of urban and suburban IMC complexes.

While suburban residents reported a slightly higher sense of freedom restriction ($M = 2.01$, $SD = 1.08$) compared to urban residents ($M = 1.81$, $SD = 1.01$), this difference was not statistically significant ($t = 1.64$, $p = 0.102$). This suggests a similarly low level of perceived restriction across both groups.

Urban residents showed significantly higher increases in the usage of sustainable transportation modes ($M = 3.32$, $SD = 1.29$) compared to suburban residents ($M = 2.42$, $SD = 1.33$; $t = -6.03$, $p < 0.001$). Additionally, urban dwellers reported feeling more encouraged to adopt sustainable mobility behaviors ($M = 3.37$, $SD = 1.17$) than their suburban counterparts ($M = 3.03$, $SD = 1.17$; $t = -2.56$, $p = 0.011$). These findings indicate that urban IMCs may be more effective in promoting active and public transport modes, possibly due to greater availability and accessibility of these options in urban environments.

Interestingly, the decision to relinquish a motor vehicle was more prevalent among suburban residents ($M = 3.23$, $SD = 1.24$) than urban residents ($M = 2.88$, $SD = 1.31$; $t = 2.43$, $p = 0.016$). This suggests that suburban IMCs may be more successful in reducing car ownership, potentially due to initially higher reliance on private vehicles in these areas.

Table 8
Frequency of Use of Shared Mobility Services (Last Six Months).

Category	Carpooling		Commercial Carsharing		Private Carsharing		Micromobility ¹		
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	
Total Sample	0.08	0.68	0.98	2.19	1.24	2.62	1.13	2.94	
Urban	IMC	0.15	1.08	1.49*	2.50	1.51	2.75	1.83*	3.81
	NIMC	0.03	0.23	0.98*	2.15	1.16	2.60	0.61*	1.99
Suburban	IMC	0.03	0.45	0.87*	2.27	1.27	2.87	1.60*	3.62
	NIMC	0.10	0.66	0.46*	1.56	1.01	2.23	0.66*	1.89

** = $p < 0.05$ in *t*-test, ¹ Micromobility variable is formed as the sum of e-bike and e-scooter sharing.

In conclusion, while urban IMCs appear more effective in encouraging sustainable transport use and behaviors, suburban IMCs seem to have a stronger influence on reducing car ownership. The perception of freedom restriction remains low in both contexts, showing that IMCs are generally not viewed as limiting personal freedom. These results (presented in detail in Table 9) highlight the importance of tailoring IMCs to the specific needs and characteristics of urban versus suburban environments.

An additional interesting finding of this study concerns the awareness of residents of either the presence or absence of an IMC in their residential complex.

Approximately 8 % of IMC residents gave a false answer and answered “No” when asked whether their residential complex had an IMC. Furthermore, 13 % of IMC residents stated not to be sure whether their complex had an IMC.

In stark contrast, approximately 29 % of NIMC residents thought their residential complex had an IMC, and 34 % were not sure whether their residential complex had an IMC.

This high degree of unawareness and uncertainty may indicate how unclear IMCs are in practice and that people may be more aware of infrastructure and concrete measures (e.g., provision of carsharing in the complex etc.) rather than the label “IMC”. Thus, the investigation of common measures associated with IMCs independent of the official housing developer-side label, is our strategy of choice of analytical strategy in the subsequent sections.

4.4. Random forest/lasso regression results

We employed Random Forest and Lasso regression analyses to quantify the impact of mobility-related measures typical for IMCs (cf. Table 4) on trip-based PMT mode share and car ownership. Across all models the parking ratio consistently emerged as the most significant predictor (for details see Table 24 and Table 25 in Appendix A8).

For the total sample, the Random Forest importance score for parking ratio was 0.890, and the Lasso coefficient was 0.109, explaining 14.4 % of the variance in PMT mode share. For car ownership, the Random Forest importance score was 0.843, with a Lasso coefficient of 0.256, showing a robust association between higher parking availability and increased car ownership, with an MSE of 0.595 and an R^2 of 13.6 %.

Car-sharing services had a smaller effect, with a Random Forest importance score of 0.020 and a Lasso coefficient of 0.009 for PMT mode share, suggesting that they complement rather than substitute car ownership. In suburban IMC areas, car-sharing showed a positive Lasso coefficient (0.087), indicating coexistence with car ownership. Parking costs also influenced PMT mode share, particularly in suburban NIMC areas, where the parking ratio explained 6.18 % of the variance. However, parking costs had a moderate effect on car ownership, with a Random Forest importance score of 0.162 and a Lasso coefficient of -0.039 .

In urban areas, the parking ratio and car-sharing services accounted for 6.84 % of the variance in PMT mode share, but car-free households showed exceptionally low model explanatory power ($R^2 = 0.0029$), suggesting other factors are more significant for them. For suburban car owners, the parking ratio and shared mobility services explained 2.20 % of the variance in PMT mode share, with the parking ratio holding an importance score of 0.307.

In IMC complexes, parking-related measures were crucial, with R^2 values ranging from 0.1304 for urban IMC car owners to 0.0654 for suburban IMC car-free households. In NIMC complexes, the parking ratio's effect was more pronounced, especially among suburban car-free households, where it explained 6.18 % of the variance in PMT share.

Overall, parking ratio was the most critical factor affecting both PMT mode share and car ownership across all groups. The Lasso model showed an R^2 of 0.144 for PMT mode share and 13.6 % for car ownership, showing that additional factors like socio-economic variables, public transport availability, and built environment characteristics may be necessary for a more comprehensive understanding of mobility behaviors. Reducing parking availability, coupled with promoting shared mobility services, appears to be an effective strategy for lowering both PMT mode share and car ownership, with other IMC measures showing only marginal impacts (Fig. 5 and Fig. 6).

4.5. Bivariate linear regression to show impacts of parking ratio on modal split and car ownership

To signify the relevance of the parking ratio or availability of parking space at residential complexes as highlighted in the Random Forest and Lasso regression analyses before, a simple bivariate regression with the average PMT mode share (whole week, trip-based) and average number of cars per household, shall shed light on the issue. As can be seen in Fig. 7 and Table 10, both car ownership and the average PMT modal share show a linear correlation with the parking ratio in the residential complexes. It must be noted that the

Table 9
T-Test Results Concerning Self-Reported Impacts of IMCs on Mobility Behavior/Choices.

Aspect/Impact	Suburban IMC Mean AVG (SD)	Urban IMC Mean AVG (SD)	T-Statistic	P-Value
I feel restricted in my freedom by the mobility concept.	2.01 (1.08)	1.81 (1.01)	1.64	0.102
I use more public transportation / bike or walk more.	2.42 (1.33)	3.32 (1.29)	-6.03	<0.001*
I feel encouraged by the mobility concept to adopt more sustainable mobility behavior.	3.03 (1.17)	3.37 (1.17)	-2.56	0.011*
It has led me to give up a motor vehicle (e.g., a second car).	3.23 (1.24)	2.88 (1.31)	2.43	0.016*

** = $p < 0.05$.

Fig. 5. Random Forest and Lasso Regression Results, IMC Measure Impacts on Outcome Variable: Car Ownership.

Fig. 6. Random Forest and Lasso Regression Results, IMC Measure Impacts on Outcome Variable: PMT Mode Share.

variance of PMT modal shares within the residential complexes' resident samples vary substantially. A linear regression using each observation in the dataset would not yield such a clear picture nor satisfactory R² values.

4.6. Multivariate regression analysis

We conducted OLS regression to identify the factors influencing PMT mode share over the course of a week, focusing on the role of IMCs alongside other variables. Ridge and Lasso regressions were also applied to manage multicollinearity and confirm the robustness

Fig. 7. Bivariate Linear Regression of Parking Ratio on Average PMT Modal Share and Car Ownership.

Table 10

Summary of Regression Model of Parking Ratio on Avg. PMT Mode Share/Avg. Car Ownership.

Metric	Number of Cars	PMT Modal Share (Whole Week, Trip-Based)
Model Formula	Parking_Ratio + intercept	Parking_Ratio + intercept
Number of Modeled Observations	19	19
Number of Filtered Observations	0	0
Model Degrees of Freedom	2	2
Residual Degrees of Freedom (DF)	17	17
SSE (Sum Squared Error)	0.4993	0.0782
MSE (Mean Squared Error)	0.0294	0.0046
R-Squared	0.7655	0.7866
Standard Error	0.1714	0.0678
p-value (Significance)	< 0.001***	< 0.001***
Key Coefficient: Parking_Ratio	0.5827 (StdErr: 0.0782, p < 0.001)	0.2450 (StdErr: 0.0309, p < 0.001)
Key Coefficient: Intercept	0.2453 (StdErr: 0.0673, p = 0.002)	0.0396 (StdErr: 0.0266, p = 0.156)

of the results. A summary of the regression results is given in Table 11, Table 12, and Table 13 below.

In terms of statistical significance, car ownership and the residential choice factor of assigning high importance to good parking availability were the most significant predictors of PMT mode share, with coefficients of 0.076 (p < 0.0001) and 0.1842 (p < 0.0001), reinforcing the link between vehicle and parking availability and increased car use. In contrast, bicycle ownership had a negative impact on PMT share (coefficient: -0.0237, p = 0.014), suggesting that bicycle ownership encourages active travel modes and reduces car dependence. The parking ratio was also a significant driver, with a coefficient of 0.0695 (p = 0.027), showing that areas with more parking spaces per household see higher PMT use, suggesting that limiting parking could reduce car reliance.

Residential choices, particularly proximity to highways, further explained PMT mode share, with coefficients of 0.098 (p = 0.012)

Table 11
Regression Model Performance Summary (DV: PMT Mode Share, Whole Week, Trip-Based).

Model	Ordinary Least Squares (OLS)
Number of Observations	441
Degrees of Freedom (Model)	19
Degrees of Freedom (Residual)	421
Adjusted R-squared	0.466
R-squared	0.489
F-statistic	21.21
Prob (F-statistic)	< 0.001
Akaike Information Criterion (AIC)	48.845
Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC)	130.626
Log-Likelihood	-4.423
Scale	0.062
Model Performance (RMSE)	
OLS	0.293
Ridge	0.258
Lasso	0.346

Table 12
Summary of OLS Regression Results.

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-value	p-value	95 % Confidence Interval
Constant	0.2088	0.0449	4.6530	<0.001	[0.1206, 0.2970]
Car_Ownership	0.0762	0.0156	4.8951	<0.001	[0.0456, 0.1068]
Normal_Bike_Ownership	-0.0237	0.0096	-2.4611	0.014	[-0.0426, -0.0048]
Parking_Ratio	0.0695	0.0312	2.2260	0.027	[0.0081, 0.1309]
Household_Income_9 (<4,000 CHF/month)	-0.1624	0.0388	-4.1869	<0.001	[-0.2386, -0.0862]
Public_Transport_Quality_3 (C)	0.0750	0.0307	2.4404	0.015	[0.0146, 0.1354]
Public_Transport_Subscription (Regional)	-0.0844	0.0333	-2.5380	0.012	[-0.1498, -0.0190]
Public_Transport_Subscription (GA)	-0.0843	0.0344	-2.4495	0.015	[-0.1519, -0.0166]
Political_Opinion_Support_for_Public_Transport_3	0.1000	0.0417	2.4001	0.017	[0.0181, 0.1819]
Residential_Choice_Proximity_to_Highway_4	0.0981	0.0391	2.5108	0.012	[0.0213, 0.1750]
Residential_Choice_Proximity_to_Highway_5	0.2289	0.0621	3.6851	<0.001	[0.1068, 0.3510]
Residential_Choice_Public_Transport_Accessibility_5	-0.0908	0.0265	-3.4329	<0.001	[-0.1428, -0.0388]
Residential_Choice_Proximity_to_Family_2	0.0848	0.0337	2.5200	0.012	[0.0187, 0.1509]
Residential_Choice_Family_Friendly_Environment_3	-0.1023	0.0352	-2.9075	0.004	[-0.1715, -0.0331]
Residential_Choice_Value_for_Money_of_Apartment_2	-0.1581	0.0763	-2.0721	0.039	[-0.3080, -0.0081]
Residential_Choice_Shared_Mobility_3	-0.0749	0.0304	-2.4609	0.014	[-0.1347, -0.0151]
Residential_Choice_Shared_Mobility_5	-0.1232	0.0455	-2.7068	0.007	[-0.2127, -0.0337]
Residential_Choice_Good_Parking_Availability_3	0.0763	0.0346	2.2026	0.028	[0.0082, 0.1443]
Residential_Choice_Good_Parking_Availability_4	0.1842	0.0380	4.8495	<0.001	[0.1096, 0.2589]
Residential_Choice_Good_Parking_Availability_5	0.1717	0.0549	3.1265	0.002	[0.0638, 0.2797]

Table 13
Variance Inflation Factors of OLS Model Variables.

Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)	Value
Car_Ownership	2.349
Normal_Bike_Ownership	3.503
Parking_Ratio	4.174
Household_Income_9 (<4,000 CHF/month)	1.134
Public_Transport_Quality_3 (C)	2.088
Public_Transport_Subscription (Regional)	1.318
Public_Transport_Subscription (GA)	1.334
Political_Opinion_Support_for_Public_Transport_3	1.221
Residential_Choice_Proximity_to_Highway_4	1.632
Residential_Choice_Proximity_to_Highway_5	1.291
Residential_Choice_Public_Transport_Accessibility_5	2.769
Residential_Choice_Proximity_to_Family_2	1.202
Residential_Choice_Family_Friendly_Environment_3	1.290
Residential_Choice_Value_for_Money_of_Apartment_2	1.098
Residential_Choice_Shared_Mobility_3	1.561
Residential_Choice_Shared_Mobility_5	1.162
Residential_Choice_Good_Parking_Availability_3	1.818
Residential_Choice_Good_Parking_Availability_4	1.963
Residential_Choice_Good_Parking_Availability_5	1.606

for level 4 and 0.229 ($p < 0.001$) for level 5.

Parking availability at residences had a strong positive association with PMT share, with coefficients increasing from 0.0763 ($p = 0.028$) to 0.1842 ($p < 0.001$) at higher availability levels, showing that convenient parking can encourage car use.

Income also played a significant role, with households earning less than CHF 4,000 per month showing a lower PMT mode share (coefficient: -0.1624 , $p < 0.001$), reflecting their greater reliance on PT or AT. Furthermore, holding a regional public transport subscription or GA travelcard significantly reduced PMT mode share, with coefficients of -0.0844 ($p = 0.012$) and -0.0843 ($p = 0.015$), respectively, underscoring the role of public transport in mitigating car use. On the other hand, poorer public transport quality in areas with a class “C” rating was associated with increased PMT use (coefficient: 0.0750, $p = 0.015$).

The model also revealed that proximity to family (coefficient: 0.085, $p = 0.012$) increased PMT mode share, while the preference to live in a family-friendly environment reduced it (coefficient: -0.102 , $p = 0.004$).

Finally, indifferent attitudes towards public transport promotion were linked to higher PMT mode share (coefficient: 0.100, $p = 0.017$).

The OLS model had an adjusted R² of 0.466, indicating that it explained nearly half of the variance in PMT mode share. The model’s RMSE was 0.293, showing a good fit. Ridge regression performed slightly better, with an RMSE of 0.258, but Lasso underperformed with an RMSE of 0.346. While Ridge regression offered marginally better predictions, OLS provided more interpretable results, identifying car ownership, parking availability, and public transport subscriptions as key influences on PMT mode share.

5. Discussion

Given that the concept of integrated mobility concepts in residential complexes is still in its developmental stages, it is essential to examine and discuss their practical implementation. As was shown in [Table 1](#) in Chapter 3, several measures frequently cited in the literature as components of an IMC are less commonly adopted in practice. These include the ban on PMT, the financial integration of public transportation subscriptions or vouchers for mobility-related services (e.g., shared mobility) into rent, the provision of on-site e-bike or scooter-sharing services, and the establishment of a mobility vision, or mobility manager/mobility management office. It must be noted, that all these instruments are present in fewer than half of the nine IMC areas analyzed. Furthermore, while five areas in the sample enforce a complete ban on car use on the premises and, in two cases, even completely restrict car ownership, the parking availability within IMC areas shows considerable variation, ranging from 0.02 to 1.27 parking spots per residential unit. This suggests that the IMC label may not necessarily reflect the presence of substantial mobility measures. Across the entire sample, no IMC complex demonstrates the use of a comprehensive array of mobility instruments. This is likely because complexes with a ban on PMT tend to be located in urban regions, where public and commercial mobility options including good PT accessibility and shared mobility offers are readily available. Notably, none of the complexes studied have implemented measures that directly target the reduction of car trips, such as a daily/monthly cap on free entrances and exits from the parking garage. This implies that these complexes are designed to reduce motorization rates, but once a resident owns a car and secures a parking space, no further disincentives or push measures are in place. Future research of IMCs and their impact would benefit vastly from the development of a standardized index of IMC “strength” which would improve the comparability of locally implemented IMC measures.

Our empirical analysis results demonstrated that the effectiveness of IMCs can vary considerably between urban and suburban spatial contexts.

In urban areas, IMCs successfully reduced both car ownership and PMT mode share. For instance, urban IMC residents made only 9 % of trips by PMT compared to 17 % in non-IMC (NIMC) complexes, and car ownership was significantly lower at 0.36 cars per household versus 0.59 in NIMC. These findings support Hypothesis 1 and Hypothesis 3 (negative correlation of IMCs with PMT mode share and car ownership), where IMCs had a clear impact on sustainable mobility behaviors. However, these effects were not mirrored in suburban settings, where no significant reduction in PMT mode share or car ownership was observed, leading to the rejection of these hypotheses in suburban contexts. This contrast suggests that IMCs may face structural challenges in less dense environments, where car dependency is higher and alternative mobility options are limited.

Our results show that IMCs are highly effective in reducing ownership and use of cars, particularly in urban areas. In several urban IMC complexes, the share of trips made by PMT was significantly lower than in NIMC complexes. These findings, in agreement with [Becker et al. \(2023\)](#); [Küchel et al. \(2024\)](#), suggest that IMCs can play an important role in fostering sustainable mobility behavior in densely populated environments. The success of IMCs in urban areas appears to be driven largely by car-free and car-reduced households. However, the study also found that IMCs have limited influence on the group of car owners, even within IMC residential complexes. Car owners continue to rely on their vehicles, showing that IMCs are most effective among those who are already inclined toward more sustainable modes of transport, while car owners remain less affected. This raises the issue of self-selection bias (cf. e.g., [Heinen et al. \(2018\)](#); [Heldt et al. \(2021\)](#); [Mokhtarian and Cao \(2008\)](#)), as individuals who choose to live in IMC complexes may already have a predisposition toward sustainable mobility behaviors. The lower PMT mode share and car ownership rates observed in urban IMCs could thus be partially attributed to a resident population that actively seeks out housing arrangements aligned with their existing mobility preferences.

As another key result, strongly concurring with other recent research ([Bauer et al., 2022](#); [Blees et al., 2023](#); [Küchel et al., 2024](#)), the critical importance of the parking availability (parking ratio) emerged during our analyses. The parking ratio proved to be a key determinant of travel behavior, particularly in urban areas, where stricter parking policies were associated with reduced car use, supporting Hypothesis 4 which posited restrictive (“push”) IMC measures exert a larger reducing impact on PMT mode share than incentivizing (“pull”) measures. When parking spaces are scarce, costly, or both, residents are more likely to reconsider car ownership, making parking policies a key lever in promoting sustainable mobility. Nevertheless, in suburban settings, reduced parking ratios

showed little effect.

Furthermore, suburban IMC residents exhibited higher daily travel distances, averaging 76 PKM per day, well above the Swiss average (30 PKM), resulting in the rejection of Hypothesis 2 that the presence of an IMC correlates negatively with the total passenger kilometers of residents. Urban IMC residents also exceeded the national average, showing that IMCs, while effective in promoting public transport and active travel, do not necessarily reduce overall travel distances.

The results also revealed heterogeneity in how different resident groups responded to IMCs, with shared mobility services playing a larger role for car-free households and parking costs being more influential for car owners, confirming Hypothesis 5 which stated that the effectiveness of IMCs on PMT mode share depends on the heterogeneity of resident groups concerning their car ownership and residential spatial type. We accept Hypothesis 5 as our analysis revealed significant differences in effects related to the influence of spatial types. The findings also highlight the diverse mobility needs of different groups, thus triggering the question how well IMCs are scalable and transferable, just as recently discussed in [Schröder and Klinger \(2024\)](#). Along with findings in earlier studies – e.g., [Küchel et al. \(2024\)](#); [Stete and Bonin \(2024\)](#) – our results suggest that a one-size-fits-all approach is not effective, but context-adjusted IMCs are necessary to maximize success.

In our data sample, residents inclined towards sustainable mobility were more likely to live in IMC complexes, particularly in urban areas, which gave a strong indication of a self-selection bias. Thus, we accept Hypothesis 6 that stated the political attitudes towards mobility and environmental issues as well as the reasons for choosing a place of residence differ significantly between residents of IMC and NIMC residential complexes. Our findings showed that environmentally conscious individuals are more likely to choose housing in IMC complexes, particularly in urban areas, as was reflected in self-reported political attitudes and the importance of residential choice factors (e.g., importance of parking availability, proximity to highway access, etc.).

Although there is no full consensus in academia, the self-selection of residents can be considered a key factor in shaping the effectiveness of IMCs, as has been suggested in related studies, such as [Bauer et al. \(2022\)](#); [Blees et al. \(2023\)](#); [Mokhtarian and Cao \(2008\)](#); [Selzer and Lanzendorf \(2022\)](#). This helps explain the greater success of IMCs in cities, where residents are already inclined toward sustainable transport behaviors and/or more willing to accept restrictions on parking availability and car use because good PT infrastructure and alternative mobility services are available. The availability and affordability of housing is often much more important to urban residents than mobility options or even IMCs, as is also reflected in the recent study by [Becker et al. \(2023\)](#) where only 6 % of residents of urban residential complexes stated that the IMC played a role in their residential location choice. In suburban areas, where residents often prioritize car access and parking availability, the impact of IMCs is more limited. This raises important questions about the potential for IMCs to expand beyond urban areas and into suburban areas, or even rural regions, where car dependency remains higher.

Lastly, we reject Hypothesis 7 positing that residents of IMC complexes perceive IMCs as a relevant restriction of freedom and therefore would be less likely to adopt more sustainable mobility behavior. Both, urban and suburban IMC residents reported to minimal restrictions on their mobility freedom, and their behavior self-reported changes towards more sustainable mobility were limited.

All abovementioned findings as well as the reasoning of the acceptance or rejection of our hypotheses are comprehensively summarized in [Table 14](#).

To conclude, IMCs have clearly proven successful in urban areas while their broader adoption faces challenges. If these concepts do not become more widespread or even mandated by policymakers, they risk remaining a niche solution limited to specific urban contexts. Nonetheless, IMCs offer promising opportunities for real estate developers, particularly in dense urban environments where parking spaces are less economically viable (see also [Bauer et al. \(2022\)](#)). When adapted to the socio-economic and spatial context of a residential complex's location outside of densely populated urbanizations, IMCs could potentially contribute to the sustainable mobility transition in suburban areas. However, the extent to which IMCs can be effective in suburban or even rural settings, and the level of demand or interest for such IMC residential complexes in non-urban environments, remains an open question. Still, as suburban and rural regions in affluent countries like Switzerland continue to grow, we strongly support the finding by [Becker et al. \(2023\)](#) arguing that mobility must be considered from day one in the planning process of new housing developments.

Our findings contribute to current global mobility trends and on-going debates on mobility policies. Over the last decades, governments at all levels have increasingly adopted the sustainable mobility paradigm in the design and implementation of transport and land-use policy measures such as the EU's urban mobility package 2013 ([European Commission, 2023](#)) to cope with urban transportation problems associated with car ownership and use ([Selzer & Lanzendorf, 2022](#)). This alternative paradigm, contrary to the conventional approach, prioritizes the social dimensions by focusing on accessibility, people and local scale. It advocates actions to promote modal shift from cars to active and sustainable modes of transport as well as to reduce travel distances. To achieve this ambition, it is vital to have public acceptability by making alternative environmentally friendly modes more attractive. This in return requires a mutually supportive package of push and pull transport policy measures ([Banister, 2008](#)) such as IMCs. In Western Europe, cities' interest in car-reduced neighborhoods is increasing, yet the implementation of car-reduced housing planning is still very modest ([Baehler & Rérat, 2020b](#); [Schröder & Klinger, 2024](#); [Selzer & Lanzendorf, 2022](#)). [May et al. \(2018\)](#) and [Heldt et al. \(2021\)](#) claimed that empirical evidence on the performance of a package (bundle) of transport policy measures is still limited. This is a pressing issue because of increasing environmental concerns ([Donais et al., 2022](#)), strong (inter)national commitments ([Fransen et al., 2023](#)) and available technologies ([Pallonetto, 2023](#)) have led to a wide range of policy measures that urban and local authorities can combine and implement for contributing to sustainable mobility ([May et al., 2018](#)).

Another trend in global mobility is mobility hubs. Both the mobility hubs and IMC concepts share a common goal; that is the integration of public transport with shared mobility services to reduce car dependency in urban areas. However, while the IMCs focus on integrated mobility planning in residential areas, mobility hubs are centered on providing multimodal mobility at strategic urban

Table 14
Summary of Hypotheses and Acceptance/Rejection Status.

H _n	Hypothesis	Status	Results/Explanation	Relevant Statistical Analyses
H ₁	The presence of an IMC is negatively correlated with the trip-based PMT mode share	(✓) Partially Accepted for urban; Rejected for suburban	Urban: IMC residents make 9 % of journeys by PMT, 8 percentage points lower than NIMC (17 %), $p < 0.05$. Suburban: No significant difference in PMT share, t -tests above 0.05. The parking ratio (availability of parking spaces) is a critical factor affecting PMT mode share.	T-tests comparing urban and suburban IMC and NIMC groups ($p < 0.05$ for urban). Multivariate OLS regression showing that parking ratio significantly impacts PMT mode share.
H ₂	An IMC correlates negatively with the total passenger kilometers of residents.	×	Hypothesis 2 was rejected as both urban and suburban IMC residents traveled significantly more kilometers than NIMC residents. Suburban IMC residents averaged 76 PKM/day compared to the national average of 30 PKM/day, and urban IMC residents also exhibited higher PKM than their NIMC counterparts ($p < 0.05$). Therefore, IMCs do not reduce total PKM, particularly in suburban settings where enhanced mobility options facilitate longer trips.	T-tests for comparison of PKM between IMC and NIMC groups ($p < 0.05$). Descriptive statistics comparing daily PKM across groups.
H ₃	An IMC correlates negatively with the car ownership rate per household.	(✓) Partially Accepted for urban; Rejected for suburban	Urban: IMC residents own 0.36 cars/household, significantly fewer than NIMC residents (0.59 cars/household), 23 percentage points lower, $p < 0.001$. Suburban: No significant difference in car ownership rates between IMC (42 %) and NIMC (61 %) households.	T-tests comparing car ownership rates in urban ($p < 0.001$) and suburban IMC vs. NIMC. Random Forest regression showing importance of parking ratio on car ownership.
H ₄	Restrictive (“push”) IMC measures exert a larger reducing impact on PMT mode share than incentivizing (“pull”) measures in IMCs.	✓ (mostly applies to urban)	Urban: Restrictive measures such as the parking ratio (ranging from 0.13 to 1.6) have a significant impact on PMT mode share reduction. Car-sharing availability is important for car-free households. Push measures like parking limitations have more influence than pull measures (e.g., car-sharing services).	Random Forest analysis of PMT mode share drivers. Bivariate regression showing the significance of parking ratio.
H ₅	The effectiveness of IMCs on PMT mode share depends on the heterogeneity of resident groups concerning their car ownership and residential spatial type.	✓ (different impacts in urban vs. suburban)	The impact of IMCs varies by resident type. Car-free households are more affected by shared mobility services, while car owners are influenced by parking costs and e-bike sharing services. Concerning Spatial Type: Significant reductions in PMT mode share ($p < 0.05$) and car ownership in urban complexes with IMCs. No significant differences in PMT mode share or car ownership in suburban IMC complexes. The effect of IMCs is more substantial in urban contexts, where mobility behavior is more constrained by external factors like parking limitations and public transport access.	Bivariate regression for PMT mode share and parking ratio. Random Forest analysis showing heterogeneous effects based on car ownership and mobility services availability. T-tests comparing urban and suburban contexts. OLS regression to determine the effect of spatial type on PMT mode share and car ownership.
H ₆	The political attitudes towards mobility and environmental issues as well as the reasons for choosing a place of residence differ significantly between residents of IMC and NIMC residential complexes.	✓ (applies to both urban and suburban, with differences in specific preferences)	Urban IMC residents show stronger support for public transport promotion (mean 4.52 vs. 4.32, $p = 0.002$) and walking/cycling improvements ($p < 0.001$) compared to NIMC residents, who prioritize road traffic improvements ($p < 0.001$). Suburban IMC residents prioritize public transport proximity, while NIMC residents prioritize parking availability ($p = 0.033$).	T-tests of political opinions and residential choice factors between IMC and NIMC. Descriptive analysis of preferences in urban and suburban settings.
H ₇	Residents of IMC complexes perceive IMCs as a relevant restriction of freedom	×	Residents in urban IMCs report slightly higher motivation toward sustainable	Likert scale survey results on perceptions of restrictions in urban and

(continued on next page)

Table 14 (continued)

H _n	Hypothesis	Status	Results/Explanation	Relevant Statistical Analyses
	and therefore they are less likely to adopt more sustainable mobility behavior.		mobility compared to suburban residents, but practical impacts are minimal, with average Likert scores around 3 out of 5. Suburban IMC residents perceive little restriction of freedom and show no significant behavior change. IMCs do not significantly affect residents' perceived freedom or behavior change toward sustainable mobility in both urban and suburban contexts.	suburban IMCs vs. NIMCs. T-tests comparing perceptions of mobility freedom and behavior change.

✓ = fully accepted, (✓) = partially accepted, × = rejected.

locations. Therefore, future research on the impacts of IMCs should take into consideration how the distance from the mobility hubs and the availability of shared mobility services at these hubs can influence travel behavior of their residents.

6. Conclusion

This study examined the effects of IMCs on residents' travel behavior in both urban and suburban residential complexes. The findings show that IMCs significantly reduce car ownership and reliance on PMT, particularly in urban areas where alternative transport options are more accessible. Urban IMC residents reported lower car ownership (0.36 cars per household) compared to those in NIMC complexes (0.59 cars per household) and made fewer trips by PMT (9 % vs. 17 % for NIMC residents). In suburban areas, however, the impact of IMCs was less clear, highlighting the continued reliance on private vehicles due to longer travel distances and less developed public transport quality.

One of the most critical factors influencing the success of IMCs is parking availability. Our results showed that lower parking ratios in IMC complexes significantly correlated with reduced car ownership and PMT usage, reinforcing the effectiveness of push measures like parking restrictions. In areas where alternative mobility options such as shared mobility services and public transport were readily available, the reduction in car dependency was even more evident.

Despite a robust methodological framework, several limitations of the study should be acknowledged. First, the sample used in this research, while large and diverse, was not fully representative of the broader population, particularly in terms of the over-representation of highly educated respondents. This could influence the generalizability of the findings, as people with higher education levels may already be more inclined towards sustainable mobility practices. Additionally, the use of an incentive – an SBB (Swiss Federal Railways) voucher – to encourage participation may have introduced a bias, potentially attracting respondents with a pre-existing preference for public transport.

The study also identified a significant self-selection bias pertaining to residential choices which was to be expected based on findings from other studies. Individuals already inclined toward sustainable transport are more likely to choose IMC complexes. This bias not only complicates the isolation of IMCs' direct impact but also constrains the broader applicability of the findings. However, the analysis still underscores the importance of parking availability and the combination of push and pull measures in influencing travel behavior.

In suburban areas, the car-reduced approach of IMCs proved less effective. Given the greater dependence on private vehicles and weaker public transport infrastructure in these areas, IMCs must be supplemented with enhanced transport options to encourage similar reductions in car use as seen in urban contexts. Future strategies could include expanding public transport services and integrating more shared and even on-demand mobility solutions in suburban regions to increase the effectiveness of IMCs.

To address the self-selection bias in residential choice, future research could employ experimental interventions, such as pilot programs that provide incentives for a broader range of residents to move into IMC complexes, or natural experiments comparing new IMCs with similar non-IMC developments. These approaches could help disentangle the direct effects of IMCs from pre-existing preferences.

Looking ahead, long-term studies are essential to assess the sustainability of these mobility changes, particularly as trends like autonomous vehicles and the continued suburban expansion evolve. Understanding whether the observed reductions in car use can be maintained in the face of such developments is critical for the future success of IMCs.

To conclude, IMCs show significant promise in reducing car dependency in urban residential complexes, though their effectiveness in suburban areas remains more limited. A tailored approach, rather than a one-size-fits-all model, is needed to optimize IMCs for different contexts. Future research should focus on adapting and scaling these concepts to foster sustainable mobility across diverse geographic and demographic environments.

Our study is unprecedented in comparing the impacts of IMCs across numerous residential complexes and is one of the first to make direct comparisons between complexes with and without IMCs at the individual resident level. By meticulously measuring residents' mobility behavior through detailed travel diaries and collecting an extensive array of demographic and socioeconomic variables, this study provides a more thorough understanding of IMC effects than previous research.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Michael Stiebe: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Widar von Arx:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Thao Thi Vu:** Writing – review & editing.

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Ethical considerations

All research procedures were conducted in compliance with ethical standards and guidelines. Informed consent was obtained from all participants involved in the study, ensuring confidentiality and anonymity. Participants were provided with clear explanations of the research objectives and their right to withdraw from the study at any point without repercussions.

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Data availability

The data supporting the findings of this study are available upon reasonable request. Due to confidentiality agreements with the survey participants, direct access to the raw data cannot be provided. However, anonymized and aggregated data are accessible for academic and research purposes by contacting the corresponding author.

Appendix A1. Description of an example IMC residential complex (Zurich Kalkbreite)

Fig. A1. Aerial View of Residential Complex Zurich Kalkbreite with IMC. Source: swisstopo.

Table 15
Features and IMC Measures of Example Residential Complex Zurich Kalkbreite.

Category	Details
Key Figures of the Settlement	
Town and Canton, Residential Complex	Zurich ZH, Kalkbreite
Spatial Type (according to ARE)	Big Centers
Spatial Category	City
Nearest Medium/Big Urban Center	Zurich
Ownership	Cooperative Kalkbreite
Year of Construction	2014
Number of Apartments	88
Usage Type	Residential and Commercial (Cinema, Gastronomy, Retail, Services, Doctor's and Therapeutic Practices, Childcare)
Explicit Mobility Concept (IMC)	Yes
Location and Mobility Offer	
Walking Distance to Basic Services	3 min
Parking Spaces for Residents/Visitors	7 / 4
Number of Bicycle Parking Spaces	330
Public Transport Quality Category (ARE)	A
Proximity to Public Transport Stops	S-Bahn station Wiedikon within a 7-minute walk, directly connected to tram and bus stops: (1) Tram Line 2 Schlieren – Tiefenbrunnen (2) Tram Line 3 Albisrieden – Klusplatz (3) Bus Line 32 Road Traffic Office – Holzerhurd
Key Figures from the Survey	
Number of Cars per Household	0.04
Number of Bicycles per Household	2.04
Possession Rate of Public Transport Subscription (GA, Network Pass) per Household	39.60 %
Share of Car-Free Households	62.50 %
Motorized Individual Transport (PMT) Distance per Person and Week	24.2 km
Bicycle Travel Distance per Person and Week	51.8 km
Walking Distance per Person and Week	17.7 km
Public Transport Distance per Person and Week	347.4 km
Mobility Measures and Aspects	Implementation in the Residential Complex
Push Measures	
Parking Space Ratio (Resident Parking Spaces per Unit)	0.125
Ban on Motorized Private Transport (PMT) in the Residential Complex (except emergency and delivery services)	Present
Active Mobility Monitoring (e.g., for violations) by Residential Complex Managers	Present
Parking Management (costs per month for parking spot in residential complex)	165 CHF / 200 CHF
Pull Measures	
Mobility Vouchers (for Public Transport / Carsharing / Bike Sharing)	Present
Bike Sharing/E-Scooter Sharing Offers in the Area	Not Present
Cargo Bike Sharing in the Area	Not Present
Carsharing Offers in the Area	Not Present
Existence of a Sustainable Mobility Vision (for the Residential Complex)	Present
Existence of a Mobility Manager/Mobility Center	Not Present
Regular Mobility Information / Workshops (at least once per year) for Residents	Present

For further information on the official IMC guidelines of Zurich Kalkbreite, please visit https://www.kalkbreite.net/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/Mobilitätskonzept-Kalkbreite_neues-Layout-2019.pdf.

Appendix A2. Travel diary from Survey

TRAVEL DIARY: MONDAY																
TRIP No.	TRIP PURPOSE				MAIN MODE OF TRANSPORT									Total Trip Distance km	ROUNDTRIP?	
	Work	Education	Leisure	Shopping/ Errands/	Car (Internal Combustion Engine, Gas, Diesel, CNG)	Electric Car/ (Plug-In) Hybrid	Motorcycle/ Moped	Bicycle	E-Bike/ E-Cargobike	(E-)Scooter	Local Public Transport	Public Transport	On Foot (from 5 minutes)		ROUNDTRIP	ONE WAY
1	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	---- km	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>				
2	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	---- km	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>				
3	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	---- km	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>				
4	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	---- km	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>				
5	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	---- km	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>				

TRAVEL DIARY: WEDNESDAY																
TRIP No.	TRIP PURPOSE				MAIN MODE OF TRANSPORT									Total Trip Distance km	ROUNDTRIP?	
	Work	Education	Leisure	Shopping/ Errands/	Car (Internal Combustion Engine, Gas, Diesel, CNG)	Electric Car/ (Plug-In) Hybrid	Motorcycle/ Moped	Bicycle	E-Bike/ E-Cargobike	(E-)Scooter	Local Public Transport	Public Transport	On Foot (from 5 minutes)		ROUNDTRIP	ONE WAY
1	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	---- km	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>				
2	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	---- km	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>				
3	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	---- km	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>				
4	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	---- km	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>				
5	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	---- km	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>				

TRAVEL DIARY: SATURDAY																
TRIP No.	TRIP PURPOSE				MAIN MODE OF TRANSPORT									Total Trip Distance km	ROUNDTRIP?	
	Work	Education	Leisure	Shopping/ Errands/	Car (Internal Combustion Engine, Gas, Diesel, CNG)	Electric Car/ (Plug-In) Hybrid	Motorcycle/ Moped	Bicycle	E-Bike/ E-Cargobike	(E-)Scooter	Local Public Transport	Public Transport	On Foot (from 5 minutes)		ROUNDTRIP	ONE WAY
1	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	---- km	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>				
2	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	---- km	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>				
3	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	---- km	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>				
4	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	---- km	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>				
5	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	---- km	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>				

Fig. A2. Travel Diary to Record Residents' Mobility (Paper Survey Layout, Translation from German Original)

Appendix A3. Political opinions and residential Choice factors

Table 16
T-Test Results Concerning Political Attitudes and Residential Choice Factors.

	Variable	Group1 ¹	Group2 ¹	Group1 Mean	Group1 Std. Dev.	Group1 n	Group2 Mean	Group2 Std. Dev.	Group2 n	t-stat.	p-value
Politics	Promotion_PT	U_IMC	U_NIMC	4.52	0.75	236	4.32	0.77	305	3.08	0.002*
		SU_IMC	SU_NIMC	4.33	0.80	174	4.24	0.80	196	1.13	0.261
	Improvements_Road_Traffic	U_IMC	U_NIMC	2.63	1.30	236	3.10	1.23	305	-4.36	0.000*
		SU_IMC	SU_NIMC	3.31	1.18	174	3.68	0.97	196	-3.29	0.001*
Improvements_Walking_Cycling	U_IMC	U_NIMC	4.58	0.78	236	4.28	0.88	305	4.12	0.000*	
	SU_IMC	SU_NIMC	4.30	0.89	174	4.24	0.78	196	0.68	0.497	
CO2_Tax	U_IMC	U_NIMC	4.26	1.10	236	3.67	1.31	305	5.54	0.000*	
	SU_IMC	SU_NIMC	3.55	1.37	174	3.35	1.31	196	1.39	0.166	
Residential Choice Factors	Proximity_Highway	U_IMC	U_NIMC	1.53	0.93	224	1.77	1.07	288	-2.74	0.006*
		SU_IMC	SU_NIMC	2.53	1.41	167	2.69	1.31	190	-1.08	0.279
	PT_Accessibility	U_IMC	U_NIMC	4.67	0.69	236	4.53	0.73	303	2.18	0.029*
		SU_IMC	SU_NIMC	4.60	0.68	171	4.57	0.71	194	0.41	0.680
	Proximity_Family	U_IMC	U_NIMC	3.18	1.18	205	3.43	1.23	267	-2.22	0.027*
		SU_IMC	SU_NIMC	3.42	1.25	149	3.27	1.32	176	1.04	0.299
	Proximity_Education	U_IMC	U_NIMC	4.01	0.91	224	3.79	1.11	267	2.32	0.021*
		SU_IMC	SU_NIMC	3.87	1.03	164	3.88	1.07	184	-0.08	0.940
	Housing_Availability	U_IMC	U_NIMC	4.28	0.79	233	4.24	0.95	297	0.53	0.596
		SU_IMC	SU_NIMC	4.02	0.88	164	4.21	0.73	192	-2.22	0.027*
	Moving_Partner_Family	U_IMC	U_NIMC	3.47	1.35	158	3.30	1.33	182	1.18	0.237
		SU_IMC	SU_NIMC	3.62	1.32	107	3.56	1.28	124	0.31	0.760
	Apartment_Complex_Attractiveness	U_IMC	U_NIMC	4.34	0.76	234	4.45	0.75	302	-1.66	0.097
		SU_IMC	SU_NIMC	4.58	0.57	170	4.35	0.68	195	3.37	0.001*
	Family_Friendly_Environment	U_IMC	U_NIMC	3.56	1.35	222	4.01	1.24	293	-3.98	0.000*
		SU_IMC	SU_NIMC	3.32	1.42	155	3.64	1.32	188	-2.13	0.034*
Price_Performance_Rental	U_IMC	U_NIMC	4.23	0.84	236	4.39	0.84	293	-2.18	0.030*	
	SU_IMC	SU_NIMC	4.14	0.94	138	4.31	0.71	193	-1.77	0.077	
Shared_Mobility	U_IMC	U_NIMC	2.97	1.29	229	2.45	1.21	271	4.63	0.000*	
	SU_IMC	SU_NIMC	2.54	1.20	158	2.14	1.10	177	3.20	0.002*	

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Table 16 (continued)

Variable	Group1 ¹	Group2 ¹	Group1 Mean	Group1 Std. Dev.	Group1 n	Group2 Mean	Group2 Std. Dev.	Group2 n	t-stat.	p-value
Good_Parking_Availability	U_IMC	U_NIMC	1.94	1.18	218	2.46	1.25	286	-4.74	0.000*
	SU_IMC	SU_NIMC	2.77	1.28	159	3.07	1.29	183	-2.14	0.033*
Walking_Cycling_Friendly_Environment	U_IMC	U_NIMC	4.21	0.90	234	4.06	0.98	300	1.87	0.062
	SU_IMC	SU_NIMC	4.04	1.00	170	4.06	0.91	194	-0.27	0.791

¹SU = suburban, U = urban.

Table 17

T-Test Results Concerning Political Attitudes and Residential Choice Factors (Differentiation by Car Ownership).

Cat	Variable	Group1 ¹	Group2 ¹	Group1 Mean	Group1 Std. Dev.	Group1 n	Group2 Mean	Group2 Std. Dev.	Group2 n	t-stat.	p-value
Politics	Promotion_PT	U_IMC_Car	U_IMC_NoCar	4.16	0.91	56	4.63	0.65	180	-4.29	0.000*
		U_NIMC_Car	U_NIMC_NoCar	4.10	0.82	154	4.54	0.64	151	-5.27	0.000*
		SU_IMC_Car	SU_IMC_NoCar	4.26	0.79	116	4.48	0.80	58	-1.75	0.081
		SU_NIMC_Car	SU_NIMC_NoCar	4.15	0.82	150	4.54	0.62	46	-3.02	0.003*
	Improvements_Road_Traffic	U_IMC_Car	U_IMC_NoCar	3.30	1.17	56	2.42	1.27	180	4.64	0.000*
		U_NIMC_Car	U_NIMC_NoCar	3.46	1.13	154	2.74	1.22	151	5.33	0.000*
		SU_IMC_Car	SU_IMC_NoCar	3.47	1.16	116	2.98	1.15	58	2.64	0.009*
		SU_NIMC_Car	SU_NIMC_NoCar	3.83	0.89	150	3.17	1.06	46	4.19	0.000*
	Improvements_Walking_Cycling	U_IMC_Car	U_IMC_NoCar	4.29	1.07	56	4.67	0.64	180	-3.30	0.001*
		U_NIMC_Car	U_NIMC_NoCar	4.13	0.91	154	4.44	0.82	151	-3.10	0.002*
		SU_IMC_Car	SU_IMC_NoCar	4.22	0.93	116	4.47	0.78	58	-1.76	0.080
		SU_NIMC_Car	SU_NIMC_NoCar	4.17	0.80	150	4.46	0.69	46	-2.16	0.032*
CO2_Tax	U_IMC_Car	U_IMC_NoCar	3.68	1.38	56	4.44	0.93	180	-4.73	0.000*	
	U_NIMC_Car	U_NIMC_NoCar	3.30	1.36	154	4.05	1.14	151	-5.26	0.000*	
	SU_IMC_Car	SU_IMC_NoCar	3.41	1.41	116	3.83	1.26	58	-1.93	0.055	
	SU_NIMC_Car	SU_NIMC_NoCar	3.25	1.32	150	3.67	1.27	46	-1.91	0.057	
Residential Choice Factors	Proximity_Highway	U_IMC_Car	U_IMC_NoCar	2.14	1.26	56	1.32	0.69	168	6.17	0.000*
		U_NIMC_Car	U_NIMC_NoCar	2.05	1.20	148	1.49	0.84	140	4.59	0.000*
		SU_IMC_Car	SU_IMC_NoCar	2.95	1.39	112	1.69	1.05	55	5.92	0.000*
		SU_NIMC_Car	SU_NIMC_NoCar	3.05	1.21	146	1.48	0.82	44	8.08	0.000*
	PT_Accessibility	U_IMC_Car	U_IMC_NoCar	4.57	0.87	56	4.70	0.62	180	-1.22	0.225
		U_NIMC_Car	U_NIMC_NoCar	4.44	0.77	153	4.63	0.67	150	-2.20	0.029*
		SU_IMC_Car	SU_IMC_NoCar	4.46	0.77	114	4.89	0.31	57	-4.15	0.000*
		SU_NIMC_Car	SU_NIMC_NoCar	4.52	0.74	149	4.76	0.57	45	-1.99	0.048*
	Proximity_Family	U_IMC_Car	U_IMC_NoCar	3.14	1.24	49	3.19	1.17	156	-0.25	0.800
		U_NIMC_Car	U_NIMC_NoCar	3.51	1.16	136	3.34	1.30	131	1.14	0.257
		SU_IMC_Car	SU_IMC_NoCar	3.38	1.29	100	3.49	1.17	49	-0.50	0.615
		SU_NIMC_Car	SU_NIMC_NoCar	3.34	1.28	133	3.05	1.41	43	1.26	0.208
	Proximity_Education	U_IMC_Car	U_IMC_NoCar	4.15	0.87	55	3.96	0.93	169	1.28	0.203
		U_NIMC_Car	U_NIMC_NoCar	3.81	1.00	134	3.78	1.21	133	0.18	0.860
		SU_IMC_Car	SU_IMC_NoCar	3.91	1.03	110	3.80	1.03	54	0.66	0.511
		SU_NIMC_Car	SU_NIMC_NoCar	3.90	1.04	143	3.83	1.18	41	0.35	0.729
	Housing_Availability	U_IMC_Car	U_IMC_NoCar	4.14	0.82	56	4.33	0.77	177	-1.54	0.125
		U_NIMC_Car	U_NIMC_NoCar	4.28	0.97	149	4.21	0.92	148	0.60	0.550
		SU_IMC_Car	SU_IMC_NoCar	3.98	0.95	108	4.09	0.75	56	-0.74	0.460
		SU_NIMC_Car	SU_NIMC_NoCar	4.18	0.77	147	4.29	0.59	45	-0.85	0.399
	Moving_Partner_Family	U_IMC_Car	U_IMC_NoCar	3.56	1.25	39	3.45	1.39	119	0.47	0.636
		U_NIMC_Car	U_NIMC_NoCar	3.40	1.26	94	3.19	1.39	88	1.07	0.285
		SU_IMC_Car	SU_IMC_NoCar	3.59	1.26	70	3.68	1.43	37	-0.34	0.738
		SU_NIMC_Car	SU_NIMC_NoCar	3.67	1.21	99	3.16	1.46	25	1.79	0.076
	Apartment_Complex_Attractiveness	U_IMC_Car	U_IMC_NoCar	4.38	0.80	56	4.33	0.75	178	0.42	0.674
		U_NIMC_Car	U_NIMC_NoCar	4.44	0.74	153	4.46	0.77	149	-0.21	0.832
		SU_IMC_Car	SU_IMC_NoCar	4.65	0.51	112	4.43	0.65	58	2.41	0.017*
		SU_NIMC_Car	SU_NIMC_NoCar	4.39	0.66	150	4.24	0.71	45	1.24	0.217
	Family_Friendly_Environment	U_IMC_Car	U_IMC_NoCar	3.58	1.36	55	3.55	1.35	167	0.15	0.883
		U_NIMC_Car	U_NIMC_NoCar	4.11	1.11	150	3.92	1.35	143	1.32	0.188
		SU_IMC_Car	SU_IMC_NoCar	3.46	1.42	107	3.02	1.41	48	1.78	0.077
		SU_NIMC_Car	SU_NIMC_NoCar	3.68	1.34	145	3.51	1.26	43	0.72	0.475
	Price_Performance_Rental	U_IMC_Car	U_IMC_NoCar	4.09	0.92	56	4.27	0.81	180	-1.43	0.155
		U_NIMC_Car	U_NIMC_NoCar	4.37	0.87	144	4.41	0.82	149	-0.42	0.676
		SU_IMC_Car	SU_IMC_NoCar	4.09	0.98	87	4.24	0.86	51	-0.86	0.389
		SU_NIMC_Car	SU_NIMC_NoCar	4.31	0.72	148	4.29	0.69	45	0.18	0.857
Shared_Mobility	U_IMC_Car	U_IMC_NoCar	2.32	1.36	56	3.17	1.20	173	-4.47	0.000*	
	U_NIMC_Car	U_NIMC_NoCar	2.29	1.10	138	2.61	1.30	133	-2.19	0.030*	
	SU_IMC_Car	SU_IMC_NoCar	2.28	1.11	102	3.00	1.24	56	-3.72	0.000*	

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Table 17 (continued)

Cat	Variable	Group1 ¹	Group2 ¹	Group1 Mean	Group1 Std. Dev.	Group1 n	Group2 Mean	Group2 Std. Dev.	Group2 n	t-stat.	p-value
Good_Parking_Availability		SU_NIMC_Car	SU_NIMC_NoCar	2.03	1.06	138	2.51	1.17	39	-2.46	0.015*
		U_IMC_Car	U_IMC_NoCar	2.75	1.29	55	1.67	1.01	163	6.34	0.000*
		U_NIMC_Car	U_NIMC_NoCar	3.09	1.15	146	1.81	1.00	140	10.06	0.000*
		SU_IMC_Car	SU_IMC_NoCar	3.14	1.28	106	2.04	0.92	53	5.61	0.000*
Walking_Cycling_Friendly_Environment		SU_NIMC_Car	SU_NIMC_NoCar	3.34	1.21	144	2.08	1.09	39	5.92	0.000*
		U_IMC_Car	U_IMC_NoCar	3.88	1.06	56	4.32	0.81	178	-3.31	0.001*
		U_NIMC_Car	U_NIMC_NoCar	4.00	0.95	151	4.12	1.01	149	-1.07	0.285
		SU_IMC_Car	SU_IMC_NoCar	3.99	0.98	112	4.12	1.03	58	-0.80	0.423
		SU_NIMC_Car	SU_NIMC_NoCar	4.04	0.93	149	4.13	0.87	45	-0.60	0.551

¹SU = suburban, U = urban.

Appendix A4. Driver’s licenses and public transport subscriptions

Table 18

T-Test Results Regarding PT Subscription and Driver’s License Ownership IMC vs. NIMC.

Spatial Type	Category	Subcategory	Significance	Mean Difference	Standard Error of Difference	95 % Confidence Interval of Difference
Urban	PT Subscriptions	GA Travel Card (GA)	0.726	0.013	0.038	[-0.061, 0.087]
		Half-Fare Card	0.022*	-0.097	0.042	[-0.180, -0.014]
		Regional Subscription	0.093	0.045	0.034	[-0.022, 0.111]
		None	0.003*	0.007	0.023	[0.017, 0.108]
	Driver’s Licenses	Car License	0.370	0.739	0.025	[-0.040, 0.056]
		Motorcycle License	0.025*	0.051	0.027	[0.000, 0.108]
		No License	0.309	0.618	0.024	[-0.060, 0.036]
Suburban	PT Subscriptions	Both Car and Motorcycle	0.033*	0.066	0.027	[-0.003, 0.104]
		GA Travel Card (GA)	0.043*	-0.057	0.033	[-0.122, 0.008]
		Half-Fare Card	0.288	0.027	0.049	[-0.068, 0.123]
		Regional Subscription	0.011*	0.088	0.039	[0.012, 0.165]
	Driver’s Licenses	None	0.446	0.005	0.036	[-0.066, 0.076]
		Car License	0.337	0.675	0.034	[-0.052, 0.081]
		Motorcycle License	0.137	0.274	0.044	[-0.038, 0.135]
		No License	0.231	0.462	0.033	[-0.089, 0.041]
		Both Car and Motorcycle	0.158	0.315	0.043	[-0.042, 0.129]

Appendix A5. Traveled distances

Table 19

Average Traveled Distances (Avg. per Day).

	Whole Week				Weekdays				Saturday				
	PMT	PT	AT	Total	PMT	PT	AT	Total	PMT	PT	AT	Total	
CH Average 2021 (km)	21.1	5.9	3.0	30.0	-	-	-	30.1	-	-	-	31.7	
Whole Sample (km)	23.7	36.1*	8.1*	67.9	19.4	33.3*	8.3	61	37.1	48.1*	8.9	94.1	
	IMC	20.1	44.4*	9.2*	73.7	15.4	40.8*	9.1	65.3	33.2	58.3*	10.5	102.0
	NIMC	26.6	29.3*	7.2*	63.2	22.7	27.1*	7.6	57.4	40.3	39.6*	7.7	87.6
Urban (km)	IMC	14.5	47.5*	9.7	71.7*	10.6	40.4	9	60	24.3	67.8*	12.3	104.4
	NIMC	18.1	30.4*	8.5	57*	12.5	28.3	9.1	49.9	33.4	40.4*	8.5	82.3
Suburban (km)	IMC	27.6	40.3	8.4*	76.3	21.8*	41.4	9.2*	72.4	45.8	44.9	7.9	98.6
	NIMC	39.7	27.7	5.3*	72.7	38.2*	25.4	5.3*	68.9	51.1	38.4	6.3	95.8

** = p < 0.05 in t-test.

Table 20

T-Test Results Concerning Average Distances Traveled (Group Comparison: IMC vs NIMC).

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Table 20 (continued)

Spatial Type	Day (s)	Mode of Transport	p-value	Mean Difference	Standard Error of Difference	95 % Confidence Interval of Difference	
Total Sample	Sat	All Modes	0.164	-14.404	10.33	[-34.681, 5.874]	
		PMT	0.309	7.131	7.003	[-6.615, 20.877]	
		PT	0.027*	-18.721	8.444	[-35.296, -2.145]	
	Mo-Su	AT	0.063	-2.814	1.514	[-5.786, 0.158]	
		All Modes	0.054	-31.487	16.327	[-63.531, 0.557]	
		PMT	0.086	6.534	3.797	[-0.918, 13.987]	
		PT	0.001*	-15.083	4.448	[-23.814, -6.353]	
		AT	0.031*	-1.947	0.902	[-3.717, -0.176]	
		All Modes	0.21	-15.79	12.587	[-40.495, 8.915]	
	Mo-Fr	PMT	0.092	7.274	4.31	[-1.185, 15.734]	
		PT	0.006*	-13.665	4.999	[-23.477, -3.853]	
		AT	0.142	-1.504	1.023	[-3.512, 0.503]	
	Urban	Sat	All Modes	0.108	-22.016	13.678	[-48.894, 4.862]
			PMT	0.289	9.15	8.626	[-7.801, 26.100]
			PT	0.017*	-27.384	11.446	[-49.877, -4.892]
Mo-Su		AT	0.08	-3.781	2.154	[-8.015, 0.452]	
		All Modes	0.035*	-44.053	20.782	[-84.880, -3.226]	
		PMT	0.427	3.623	4.556	[-5.327, 12.572]	
Mo-Fr		PT	0.003*	-17.051	5.706	[-28.260, -5.841]	
		AT	0.304	-1.256	1.22	[-3.654, 1.141]	
		All Modes	0.185	-20.07	15.138	[-49.810, 9.670]	
Suburban		Sat	PMT	0.682	1.916	4.67	[-7.259, 11.091]
			PT	0.051	-12.069	6.172	[-24.196, 0.058]
			AT	0.929	0.118	1.318	[-2.472, 2.708]
		Mo-Su	All Modes	0.859	-2.802	15.725	[-33.743, 28.138]
			PMT	0.654	5.247	11.704	[-17.783, 28.277]
			PT	0.597	-6.491	12.267	[-30.627, 17.645]
	Mo-Fr	AT	0.428	-1.559	1.962	[-5.420, 2.303]	
		All Modes	0.673	-11.066	26.225	[-62.639, 40.507]	
		PMT	0.059	12.087	6.388	[-0.476, 24.649]	
	Mo-Fr	PT	0.076	-12.661	7.106	[-26.635, 1.313]	
		AT	0.019*	-3.115	1.317	[-5.704, -0.525]	
		All Modes	0.738	-7.199	21.515	[-49.512, 35.114]	
		PMT	0.039*	16.379	7.916	[0.812, 31.947]	
		PT	0.057	-16.017	8.373	[-32.483, 0.450]	
		AT	0.014*	-3.962	1.61	[-7.128, -0.796]	

Appendix A6. Modal splits

Table 21
Trip-Based and Distance-Based Modal Splits.

Category	Group	Whole Week			Weekdays			Saturday			
		PMT	PT	AT	PMT	PT	AT	PMT	PT	AT	
Trip-Based (in %)	Whole Sample	22	34	44	19	34	47	29	32	39	
	Urban	IMC	9*	37*	54	7*	36	57	12*	41*	47
		NIMC	17*	35*	48	15*	34	51	23*	34*	43
	Suburban	IMC	35	31	34	31	33	36	43	26	31
NIMC		35	31	34	34	34	38	45	26	30	
Distance-Based (in %)	Whole Sample	28	44	28	21	42	37	30	36	34	
	Urban	IMC	13*	52*	35	8*	45	47	13*	47*	41
		NIMC	25*	43*	32	18*	41	41	26*	36*	38
	Suburban	IMC	39	40	21	32	41	27	43	30	27
		NIMC	42	39	19	32	40	27	47	28	25

** = p < 0.05 in t-test.

Table 22
T-Test Results Comparing Modal Splits.

Spatial Type	Time Period	Mode of Transport	Significance (trip-based)	Mean Difference (trip-based)	Standard Error of Difference (trip-based)	95 %-Confidence Interval of Difference (trip-based)	Significance (distance-based)	Mean Difference (distance-based)	Standard Error of Difference (distance-based)	95 %-Confidence Interval of Difference (distance-based)	
Urban	Sat	PMT	0.001*	-0.092	0.039	[-0.167, -0.016]	<0.001*	-0.106	0.042	[-0.188, -0.024]	
		PT	0.055	0.068	0.050	[-0.030, 0.165]	0.010*	0.099	0.054	[-0.007, 0.206]	
		AT	0.215	0.046	0.052	[-0.057, 0.149]	0.448	0.029	0.054	[-0.076, 0.134]	
	Mo-Su	PMT	<0.001*	-0.083	0.029	[-0.141, -0.026]	<0.001*	-0.117	0.039	[-0.194, -0.040]	
		PT	0.387	0.025	0.041	[-0.055, 0.105]	0.015*	0.087	0.051	[-0.012, 0.187]	
		AT	0.091	0.052	0.043	[-0.033, 0.137]	0.472	0.024	0.046	[-0.067, 0.114]	
	Mo-Fr	PMT	0.001*	-0.073	0.029	[-0.131, -0.015]	<0.001*	-0.091	0.035	[-0.159, -0.023]	
		PT	0.557	0.019	0.045	[-0.070, 0.108]	0.288	0.040	0.053	[-0.064, 0.143]	
		AT	0.075	0.062	0.049	[-0.034, 0.158]	0.115	0.059	0.053	[-0.044, 0.163]	
	Suburban	Sat	PMT	0.690	-0.019	0.067	[-0.151, 0.113]	0.503	-0.033	0.069	[-0.168, 0.102]
			PT	0.938	-0.003	0.054	[-0.108, 0.103]	0.818	0.010	0.060	[-0.107, 0.126]
			AT	0.825	0.009	0.057	[-0.104, 0.122]	0.805	0.010	0.057	[-0.102, 0.122]
Mo-Su		PMT	0.912	-0.004	0.056	[-0.113, 0.105]	0.421	-0.035	0.062	[-0.156, 0.086]	
		PT	0.990	0.000	0.049	[-0.096, 0.096]	0.837	0.009	0.060	[-0.109, 0.126]	
		AT	0.898	-0.004	0.049	[-0.100, 0.091]	0.562	0.018	0.044	[-0.068, 0.104]	
Mo-Fr		PMT	0.591	0.022	0.057	[-0.091, 0.134]	0.957	0.002	0.062	[-0.118, 0.123]	
		PT	0.973	-0.001	0.056	[-0.112, 0.109]	0.885	0.007	0.065	[-0.120, 0.133]	
		AT	0.720	-0.014	0.056	[-0.124, 0.095]	0.946	-0.003	0.056	[-0.112, 0.107]	

Appendix A7. Shared mobility use

Table 23
T-Test Results Regarding Frequency of Shared Mobility Usage.

Spatial Type	Mode of Transport	Significance	Mean Difference	Standard Error of Difference	95 %-Confidence Interval of Difference
Urban	E-Bike	0.011*	-0.457	0.205	[-0.860, -0.053]
	E-Scooter	<0.001*	-0.756	0.162	[-1.076, -0.437]
	Carpooling	0.022*	-0.128	0.072	[-0.270, 0.013]
	Carsharing (Commercial)	0.006*	-0.508	0.204	[-0.909, -0.107]
	Carsharing (Private)	0.064	-0.353	0.233	[-0.811, 0.104]
	Micromobility ¹	<0.001*	-1.213	0.273	[-1.750, -0.676]
Suburban	E-Bike	<0.001*	-1.139	0.261	[-1.654, -0.625]
	E-Scooter	0.074	0.195	0.132	[-0.065, 0.454]
	Carpooling	0.13	0.068	0.059	[-0.048, 0.183]
	Carsharing (Commercial)	0.021*	-0.412	0.205	[-0.816, -0.008]
	Carsharing (Private)	0.165	-0.26	0.27	[-0.790, 0.263]
	Micromobility ¹	<0.001*	-0.945	0.306	[-1.547, -0.343]

¹Micromobility variable is formed as the sum of e-bike and e-scooter sharing.

Appendix A8. Random Forest/Lasso regression results

Table 24
Random Forest and Lasso Regression Results Regarding Influence of IMC Measures on PMT Modal Share, Distinction of Groups by Car Ownership.

Group	Variable	Random Forest Importance	Lasso Coefficient	Lasso MSE	Lasso R ²	Lasso Non-Zero Coefs
Urban Car Owners	Parking ratio	0.665	0.062	0.103	0.068	7
	Car-sharing services_1	0.098	0.025	0.103	0.068	7
	Sustainable mobility vision_1	0.004	-0.007	0.103	0.068	7
	Bike-sharing/e-scooter-sharing services_1	0.010	0.006	0.103	0.068	7
	Parking costs	0.098	-0.005	0.103	0.068	7

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Table 24 (continued)

Group	Variable	Random Forest Importance	Lasso Coefficient	Lasso MSE	Lasso R ²	Lasso Non-Zero Coefs	
Urban Car-Free	Mobility manager/center_1	0.010	-0.004	0.103	0.068	7	
	Ban on PMT_1	0.031	-0.001	0.103	0.068	7	
	Mobility information/workshops_1	0.020	0.000	0.103	0.068	7	
	Cargo bike sharing_1	0.014	0.000	0.103	0.068	7	
	Mobility vouchers_1	0.014	0.000	0.103	0.068	7	
	Mobility monitoring_1	0.035	0.000	0.103	0.068	7	
	Car-sharing services_1	0.147	-0.002	0.016	0.003	1	
	Mobility information/workshops_1	0.037	0.000	0.016	0.003	1	
	Mobility manager/center_1	0.023	0.000	0.016	0.003	1	
	Sustainable mobility vision_1	0.015	0.000	0.016	0.003	1	
	Cargo bike sharing_1	0.017	0.000	0.016	0.003	1	
	Bike-sharing/e-scooter-sharing services_1	0.024	0.000	0.016	0.003	1	
	Mobility vouchers_1	0.046	0.000	0.016	0.003	1	
	Mobility monitoring_1	0.079	0.000	0.016	0.003	1	
Suburban Car Owners	Ban on PMT_1	0.066	0.000	0.016	0.003	1	
	Parking costs	0.247	0.000	0.016	0.003	1	
	Parking ratio	0.300	0.000	0.016	0.003	1	
	Parking ratio	0.583	0.040	0.143	0.022	2	
	Car-sharing services_1	0.107	0.037	0.143	0.022	2	
	Mobility information/workshops_1	0.030	0.000	0.143	0.022	2	
	Mobility manager/center_1	0.009	0.000	0.143	0.022	2	
	Sustainable mobility vision_1	0.008	0.000	0.143	0.022	2	
	Cargo bike sharing_1	0.008	0.000	0.143	0.022	2	
	Bike-sharing/e-scooter-sharing services_1	0.006	0.000	0.143	0.022	2	
	Mobility vouchers_1	0.006	0.000	0.143	0.022	2	
	Mobility monitoring_1	0.003	0.000	0.143	0.022	2	
	Ban on PMT_1	0.000	0.000	0.143	0.022	2	
	Parking costs	0.240	0.000	0.143	0.022	2	
Suburban Car-Free	Parking ratio	0.572	0.018	0.023	0.045	2	
	Car-sharing services_1	0.149	0.016	0.023	0.045	2	
	Mobility information/workshops_1	0.008	0.000	0.023	0.045	2	
	Mobility manager/center_1	0.006	0.000	0.023	0.045	2	
	Sustainable mobility vision_1	0.002	0.000	0.023	0.045	2	
	Cargo bike sharing_1	0.010	0.000	0.023	0.045	2	
	Bike-sharing/e-scooter-sharing services_1	0.012	0.000	0.023	0.045	2	
	Mobility vouchers_1	0.009	0.000	0.023	0.045	2	
	Mobility monitoring_1	0.014	0.000	0.023	0.045	2	
	Ban on PMT_1	0.000	0.000	0.023	0.045	2	
	Parking costs	0.217	0.000	0.023	0.045	2	
	Parking ratio	0.487	0.053	0.089	0.130	5	
	Bike-sharing/e-scooter-sharing services_1	0.241	0.033	0.089	0.130	5	
	Cargo bike sharing_1	0.057	0.022	0.089	0.130	5	
Urban IMC Car Owners	Mobility manager/center_1	0.023	-0.016	0.089	0.130	5	
	Sustainable mobility vision_1	0.015	-0.015	0.089	0.130	5	
	Mobility information/workshops_1	0.008	0.000	0.089	0.130	5	
	Car-sharing services_1	0.064	0.000	0.089	0.130	5	
	Mobility vouchers_1	0.017	0.000	0.089	0.130	5	
	Mobility monitoring_1	0.025	0.000	0.089	0.130	5	
	Ban on PMT_1	0.037	0.000	0.089	0.130	5	
	Parking costs	0.026	0.000	0.089	0.130	5	
	Urban IMC Car-Free	Mobility information/workshops_1	0.011	0.000	0.011	0.000	0
		Mobility manager/center_1	0.084	0.000	0.011	0.000	0
		Sustainable mobility vision_1	0.063	0.000	0.011	0.000	0
		Car-sharing services_1	0.016	0.000	0.011	0.000	0
		Cargo bike sharing_1	0.017	0.000	0.011	0.000	0
		Bike-sharing/e-scooter-sharing services_1	0.047	0.000	0.011	0.000	0
Mobility vouchers_1		0.032	0.000	0.011	0.000	0	
Mobility monitoring_1		0.073	0.000	0.011	0.000	0	
Ban on PMT_1		0.039	0.000	0.011	0.000	0	
Parking costs		0.203	0.000	0.011	0.000	0	
Parking ratio		0.415	0.000	0.011	0.000	0	
Urban NIMC Car Owners		Parking ratio	0.593	0.042	0.107	0.048	3
		Ban on PMT_1	0.092	0.022	0.107	0.048	3
		Parking costs	0.263	-0.020	0.107	0.048	3

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Table 24 (continued)

Group	Variable	Random Forest Importance	Lasso Coefficient	Lasso MSE	Lasso R ²	Lasso Non-Zero Coefs
Urban NIMC Car-Free	Mobility information/workshops_1	0.000	0.000	0.107	0.048	3
	Mobility manager/center_1	0.000	0.000	0.107	0.048	3
	Sustainable mobility vision_1	0.000	0.000	0.107	0.048	3
	Car-sharing services_1	0.039	0.000	0.107	0.048	3
	Cargo bike sharing_1	0.014	0.000	0.107	0.048	3
	Bike-sharing/e-scooter-sharing services_1	0.000	0.000	0.107	0.048	3
	Mobility vouchers_1	0.000	0.000	0.107	0.048	3
	Mobility monitoring_1	0.000	0.000	0.107	0.048	3
	Car-sharing services_1	0.497	-0.017	0.023	0.027	1
	Mobility information/workshops_1	0.000	0.000	0.023	0.027	1
	Mobility manager/center_1	0.000	0.000	0.023	0.027	1
	Sustainable mobility vision_1	0.000	0.000	0.023	0.027	1
	Cargo bike sharing_1	0.009	0.000	0.023	0.027	1
	Bike-sharing/e-scooter-sharing services_1	0.000	0.000	0.023	0.027	1
Suburban IMC Car Owners	Mobility vouchers_1	0.000	0.000	0.023	0.027	1
	Mobility monitoring_1	0.000	0.000	0.023	0.027	1
	Ban on PMT_1	0.038	0.000	0.023	0.027	1
	Parking costs	0.340	0.000	0.023	0.027	1
	Parking ratio	0.116	0.000	0.023	0.027	1
	Car-sharing services_1	0.211	0.040	0.153	0.034	2
	Parking ratio	0.351	0.038	0.153	0.034	2
	Mobility information/workshops_1	0.102	0.000	0.153	0.034	2
	Mobility manager/center_1	0.012	0.000	0.153	0.034	2
	Sustainable mobility vision_1	0.094	0.000	0.153	0.034	2
	Cargo bike sharing_1	0.006	0.000	0.153	0.034	2
	Bike-sharing/e-scooter-sharing services_1	0.017	0.000	0.153	0.034	2
	Mobility vouchers_1	0.027	0.000	0.153	0.034	2
	Mobility monitoring_1	0.022	0.000	0.153	0.034	2
Suburban IMC Car-Free	Ban on PMT_1	0.000	0.000	0.153	0.034	2
	Parking costs	0.158	0.000	0.153	0.034	2
	Parking ratio	0.379	0.015	0.017	0.065	2
	Car-sharing services_1	0.174	0.014	0.017	0.065	2
	Mobility information/workshops_1	0.088	0.000	0.017	0.065	2
	Mobility manager/center_1	0.005	0.000	0.017	0.065	2
	Sustainable mobility vision_1	0.129	0.000	0.017	0.065	2
	Cargo bike sharing_1	0.007	0.000	0.017	0.065	2
	Bike-sharing/e-scooter-sharing services_1	0.019	0.000	0.017	0.065	2
	Mobility vouchers_1	0.019	0.000	0.017	0.065	2
	Mobility monitoring_1	0.027	0.000	0.017	0.065	2
	Ban on PMT_1	0.000	0.000	0.017	0.065	2
	Parking costs	0.153	0.000	0.017	0.065	2
	Parking ratio	0.684	0.026	0.134	0.016	2
Suburban NIMC Car Owners	Parking costs	0.316	-0.016	0.134	0.016	2
	Mobility information/workshops_1	0.000	0.000	0.134	0.016	2
	Mobility manager/center_1	0.000	0.000	0.134	0.016	2
	Sustainable mobility vision_1	0.000	0.000	0.134	0.016	2
	Car-sharing services_1	0.000	0.000	0.134	0.016	2
	Cargo bike sharing_1	0.000	0.000	0.134	0.016	2
	Bike-sharing/e-scooter-sharing services_1	0.000	0.000	0.134	0.016	2
	Mobility vouchers_1	0.000	0.000	0.134	0.016	2
	Mobility monitoring_1	0.000	0.000	0.134	0.016	2
	Ban on PMT_1	0.000	0.000	0.134	0.016	2
	Parking ratio	0.817	0.034	0.029	0.062	1
	Mobility information/workshops_1	0.000	0.000	0.029	0.062	1
	Mobility manager/center_1	0.000	0.000	0.029	0.062	1
	Sustainable mobility vision_1	0.000	0.000	0.029	0.062	1
Suburban NIMC Car-Free	Car-sharing services_1	0.000	0.000	0.029	0.062	1
	Cargo bike sharing_1	0.000	0.000	0.029	0.062	1
	Bike-sharing/e-scooter-sharing services_1	0.000	0.000	0.029	0.062	1
	Mobility vouchers_1	0.000	0.000	0.029	0.062	1
	Mobility monitoring_1	0.000	0.000	0.029	0.062	1
	Ban on PMT_1	0.000	0.000	0.029	0.062	1
	Parking costs	0.183	0.000	0.029	0.062	1

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Table 24 (continued)

Group	Variable	Random Forest Importance	Lasso Coefficient	Lasso MSE	Lasso R ²	Lasso Non-Zero Coefs
Total Sample	Parking ratio	0.890	0.109	0.092	0.144	3
	Ban on PMT_1	0.011	-0.014	0.092	0.144	3
	Car-sharing services_1	0.020	0.009	0.092	0.144	3
	Mobility information/workshops_1	0.005	0.000	0.092	0.144	3
	Mobility manager/center_1	0.002	0.000	0.092	0.144	3
	Sustainable mobility vision_1	0.004	0.000	0.092	0.144	3
	Cargo bike sharing_1	0.000	0.000	0.092	0.144	3
	Bike-sharing/e-scooter-sharing services_1	0.001	0.000	0.092	0.144	3
	Mobility vouchers_1	0.002	0.000	0.092	0.144	3
	Mobility monitoring_1	0.003	0.000	0.092	0.144	3
	Parking costs	0.061	0.000	0.092	0.144	3

Table 25

Random Forest and Lasso Regression Results Regarding Influence of IMC Measures on Car Ownership.

Group	Variable	Random Forest Importance	Lasso Coefficient	Lasso MSE	Lasso R ²	Lasso Non-Zero Coefs	
Whole Sample	Parking ratio	0.843	0.256	0.595	0.136	5	
	Ban on PMT_1	0.021	-0.057	0.595	0.136	5	
	Sustainable mobility vision_1	0.018	-0.046	0.595	0.136	5	
	Car-sharing services_1	0.017	0.030	0.595	0.136	5	
	Mobility information/workshops_1	0.008	-0.006	0.595	0.136	5	
	Mobility manager/center_1	0.002	0.000	0.595	0.136	5	
	Cargo bike sharing_1	0.003	0.000	0.595	0.136	5	
	Bike-sharing/e-scooter-sharing services_1	0.002	0.000	0.595	0.136	5	
	Mobility vouchers_1	0.011	0.000	0.595	0.136	5	
	Mobility monitoring_1	0.010	0.000	0.595	0.136	5	
	Parking costs	0.063	0.000	0.595	0.136	5	
	Urban IMC	Parking ratio	0.448	0.148	0.919	0.052	5
		Sustainable mobility vision_1	0.167	-0.108	0.919	0.052	5
Mobility monitoring_1		0.043	-0.034	0.919	0.052	5	
Mobility information/workshops_1		0.014	-0.016	0.919	0.052	5	
Mobility manager/center_1		0.020	-0.002	0.919	0.052	5	
Car-sharing services_1		0.032	0.000	0.919	0.052	5	
Cargo bike sharing_1		0.072	0.000	0.919	0.052	5	
Bike-sharing/e-scooter-sharing services_1		0.035	0.000	0.919	0.052	5	
Mobility vouchers_1		0.014	0.000	0.919	0.052	5	
Ban on PMT_1		0.096	0.000	0.919	0.052	5	
Parking costs		0.059	0.000	0.919	0.052	5	
Urban NIMC		Parking ratio	0.710	0.093	0.432	0.045	4
		Cargo bike sharing_1	0.060	-0.056	0.432	0.045	4
	Parking costs	0.162	-0.039	0.432	0.045	4	
	Car-sharing services_1	0.027	-0.013	0.432	0.045	4	
	Mobility information/workshops_1	0.000	0.000	0.432	0.045	4	
	Mobility manager/center_1	0.000	0.000	0.432	0.045	4	
	Sustainable mobility vision_1	0.000	0.000	0.432	0.045	4	
	Bike-sharing/e-scooter-sharing services_1	0.000	0.000	0.432	0.045	4	
	Mobility vouchers_1	0.000	0.000	0.432	0.045	4	
	Mobility monitoring_1	0.000	0.000	0.432	0.045	4	
	Ban on PMT_1	0.041	0.000	0.432	0.045	4	
	Suburban IMC	Parking ratio	0.307	0.258	0.572	0.147	2
		Car-sharing services_1	0.023	0.087	0.572	0.147	2
Mobility information/workshops_1		0.264	0.000	0.572	0.147	2	
Mobility manager/center_1		0.010	0.000	0.572	0.147	2	
Sustainable mobility vision_1		0.320	0.000	0.572	0.147	2	
Cargo bike sharing_1		0.013	0.000	0.572	0.147	2	
Bike-sharing/e-scooter-sharing services_1		0.016	0.000	0.572	0.147	2	
Mobility vouchers_1		0.021	0.000	0.572	0.147	2	
Mobility monitoring_1		0.014	0.000	0.572	0.147	2	
Ban on PMT_1		0.000	0.000	0.572	0.147	2	
Parking costs		0.012	0.000	0.572	0.147	2	

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Table 25 (continued)

Group	Variable	Random Forest Importance	Lasso Coefficient	Lasso MSE	Lasso R ²	Lasso Non-Zero Coefs
	Parking ratio	0.700	0.169	0.441	0.097	2
	Parking costs	0.300	-0.053	0.441	0.097	2
	Mobility information/workshops_1	0.000	0.000	0.441	0.097	2
	Mobility manager/center_1	0.000	0.000	0.441	0.097	2
	Sustainable mobility vision_1	0.000	0.000	0.441	0.097	2
	Car-sharing services_1	0.000	0.000	0.441	0.097	2
	Cargo bike sharing_1	0.000	0.000	0.441	0.097	2
	Bike-sharing/e-scooter-sharing services_1	0.000	0.000	0.441	0.097	2
	Mobility vouchers_1	0.000	0.000	0.441	0.097	2
	Mobility monitoring_1	0.000	0.000	0.441	0.097	2
	Ban on PMT_1	0.000	0.000	0.441	0.097	2

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